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Evidence on health inequities experienced by the rare disease community with regards to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services: a scoping review

Final report

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Requests for access to data should be addressed to the corresponding author.

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Guarantor of the review

Jo Thompson Coon

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Abbreviations

ALS	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
DARE	Database of Abstracts and Reviews of Effects
DHSC	Department of Health and Social Care
DMD	Duchenne muscular dystrophy
EU	European Union
ICS	Integrated care systems
IPF	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis
LMIC	Low- and middle-income countries
MeSH	Medical Subject Headings
MND	Motor Neuron Disease
MRKH	Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome
MSA	Multiple system atrophy
NHS	National Health Service
NIHR	National Institute for Health and Social Care Research
ORE	Open Research Exeter
PICo	Population/problem, phenomenon of Interest, Context
PERSPEX	Public Engagement in Research for health and Social Policy at Exeter
POEMS	Polyneuropathy Organomegaly Endocrinopathy Monoclonal gammopathy Skin changes
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PROGRESS+	Place of residence, race/ethnicity, gender, religion, education, socioeconomic status, social capital (+ age, disability)
PRP	Policy Research Programme
RDCN	Rare Disease Collaborative Network

SWAN Syndrome without a name

UK United Kingdom

USA United States of America

Executive summary

Rare diseases are diseases which affect fewer than one in 2000 people. Although rare diseases are individually rare, they are collectively common, affecting around one in 17 people in the UK.¹ The Orphanet website (<https://www.orpha.net/>) lists around 7000 documented rare diseases, ranging from relatively common rare diseases such as motor neurone disease (MND), sickle cell disease and cystic fibrosis, to ultra-rare diseases such as POEMS syndrome, which affects around one in 300,000 people. Seventy-five percent of rare diseases affect children, and around 30% of children with a rare disease die before reaching five years of age.²

Evidence gathered from surveys and workshops conducted in the UK has found that people living with a rare disease face many challenges with accessing health and social care services.³ This can arise due to factors such as a lack of knowledge amongst clinicians to support timely diagnosis and appropriate treatment, and limited access to specialist centres where appropriate care is provided. Evidence also shows that the diagnosis of rare diseases can take a long time, during which the symptoms may get progressively worse. Furthermore, these experiences are exacerbated for some people within the rare disease community, including ethnic minorities, women and according to socioeconomic status and where you live.³

These experiences indicate that people with a rare disease may have worse health outcomes than people in the general population due to the limited services and support available to them. The experiences also point to unequal support within the rare disease community itself.

Differences in health opportunities (such as service access) and outcomes (such as morbidity) which are systematic, avoidable and unfair are defined as *health inequities*, which are important to address to ensure that services are equitable for all people in the UK.⁴

What did we want to know?

The UK Rare Diseases Framework and England's Rare Disease Action Plans are committed to addressing health inequities associated with rare diseases.⁵⁻⁷ The Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility were asked to carry out a review which systematically gathers together published research and grey literature which describes the nature and extent of health inequities experienced between the rare disease community and the general population, and within the rare disease community, with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and access to services. This could help to inform how to address health inequities associated with rare diseases.

Aim and objectives

Aim

Our review aimed to identify and summarise evidence on health inequities experienced within the rare disease community or between the rare disease community and general population with regards to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services.

Objectives

1. To carry out a scoping review which will systematically identify and describe the available evidence on health inequities experienced within the rare disease community or between the rare disease community and general population with regards to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services.
2. To draw out findings relevant to the UK context.

What did we find?

Key characteristics of included studies

We identified 136 studies which report data relating to the experience of inequity in the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis or access to services. These comprise of 96 primary studies conducted in the UK, and 40 systematic reviews which include studies conducted both in the UK and around the world.

The most frequently reported rare diseases in the identified UK primary studies and systematic reviews were MND and sickle cell disease. Some studies included multiple rare diseases, including more than 100 rare diseases in several studies. It was not possible to ascertain the number of rare diseases represented in the review, as the names of diseases were not always reported in the identified studies.

Most of the UK primary studies included both male and female participants (66%), with a small proportion of studies focusing on one gender (10% on female participants only; 1% on male participants only). The remainder did not report gender. Adults (≥ 18 years of age) were the most frequently occurring age group in the UK primary studies (41%), with an additional 32% of studies reporting data on both adults and children and 18% reporting data solely on children. Ethnicity was reported in 24% of UK primary studies. The characteristics of participants in systematic reviews were similar to the UK primary studies.

Around half of the UK primary studies were qualitative studies (52%), with a smaller proportion of quantitative studies (22%) and mixed methods studies (26%). Most of the systematic reviews

included multiple study designs (75%). Twenty percent included solely qualitative studies and 5% included solely quantitative studies.

Types of inequity

We identified 17 types of inequity across the 136 UK primary studies and systematic reviews. These included 11 types of inequity which were identified across the rare disease community and six types of inequity which were identified in subgroups within the rare disease community. The latter were identified using the PROGRESS+ framework, which sets out characteristics which stratify health opportunities and outcomes.⁸

The 11 types of identified inequity which are shared across the rare disease community were:

1. Delayed diagnosis

Experiencing delays to receiving a diagnosis.

2. Lack of knowledge

A lack of knowledge about rare diseases amongst health and social care professionals which hinders diagnosis and access to services, which can also include dismissive attitudes towards symptoms of rare diseases.

3. Lack of information

A lack of signposting by health and social care professionals to relevant and sufficient information about rare diseases.

4-9. Limited service provision

Limited service provision in several areas including (4) mental health services, (5) emergency services, (6) dentistry services, (7) specialist services and (8) social care services. There was also a category for (9) services in general where no specific service was mentioned in the data. (Data relating to affordability of services was captured under socioeconomic inequities, below).

10. Limited services for undiagnosed conditions

Specific challenges around accessing services for people with symptoms of a rare disease but without a diagnosis.

11. Lack of care co-ordination

Lack of care co-ordination between primary, secondary, specialist and social care services, which can adversely affect the receipt of a diagnosis and accessing services.

In addition, we identified six characteristics of subgroups in the rare disease community which lead to inequity: (1) place of residence; (2) race/ethnicity; (3) gender; (4) socioeconomic status; (5) age; (6) disability.

All of these types of inequity could be experienced both *between the general population and the rare disease community*, and *within the rare disease community itself*. This is illustrated in Table 1. The main report is structured around these headers to make it clear where the inequity is being experienced.

Table 1. How the categories of identified inequities overlap, with examples.

	Inequities between the rare disease community and the general population	Inequities within the rare disease community
Inequities shared across the rare disease community (n=11)	e.g. lack of knowledge amongst clinicians about rare diseases compared to more common diseases.	e.g. lack of knowledge amongst clinicians about rare diseases which is comparatively worse for some rare diseases than others.
Inequities experienced by subgroups in the rare disease community* (n=6)	e.g. ethnic minorities experience specific challenges with accessing services for sickle cell disease compared to the general population.	e.g. ethnic minorities experience specific challenges with accessing services for sickle cell disease which are not experienced by others in the rare disease community.

*Groups identified with reference to PROGRESS+, i.e. place of residence, race/ethnicity, gender, socioeconomic status, age, disability.

Summary of inequities experienced by the rare disease community

Overall, the majority of evidence of inequities related to the rare disease community as a whole compared with the general population. However, the data in UK primary studies and systematic reviews which indicated these types of inequity were not always comparative, which means that they were not comparing the experiences of the rare disease community with the general population. Instead, the studies mainly reported experiences which are specific to people living with a rare disease and their carers, and we have therefore suggested that the data were *indicative* of inequities. For example, the experience of lack of knowledge of rare diseases amongst clinicians is unlikely to be experienced by the general population with respect to more common diseases, which are likely to be better understood by clinicians. Similarly, the experiences of delayed diagnosis may be worse for the rare disease community due to lack of knowledge amongst clinicians.

Some of the experiences of the rare disease community may also be experienced by people in the general population. As such, for some of the identified experiences, we are less confident that these are experiences of inequity. For example, the identified lack of care co-ordination may be experienced by others in the general population with complex needs.⁹ The identified lack of access to mental health services may also be a problem amongst the general population.¹⁰ Thus, these findings should be interpreted with caution within the wider context of service access for the general population.

We also identified data on how these inequities are experienced differently within the rare disease community, albeit there were fewer examples of this. This included comparative data which showed greater satisfaction of clinician knowledge and information provision in specialist centres compared with non-specialist services when receiving a diagnosis of cystic fibrosis, MND and sickle cell disease.^{11, 12} Comparative data also showed a minority of people with a rare disease have access to a specialist service.¹³⁻¹⁶

Furthermore, the data showed that experiences of inequity for people with a rare disease are exacerbated for subgroups according to characteristics identified in the PROGRESS+ framework.⁸ For example, dismissive attitudes towards the symptoms of ethnic minorities and women were reported in qualitative studies, including the perception amongst women that the symptoms of rare diseases are dismissed by clinicians as part of normal menstrual health,¹⁷ and the perception amongst ethnic minorities that they are mistrusted by clinicians when experiencing pain related to sickle cell disease.¹⁸ There was also evidence that services for rare diseases are difficult to access due to geographical reasons, and that this could be exacerbated by socioeconomic status.^{19, 20}

Implications

This review has highlighted a need for more research on health inequities experienced by the rare disease community. Importantly, this needs to include research on the less common rare diseases, including ultra-rare diseases.

Interventions are required to address the inequities which we were able to identify. Future development of any such interventions can build on the ongoing work listed below:

- Education resources for clinicians in development by the National Genomics Education Programme, including the GeNotes tool and the Rare Disease Education Hub.
- The development of Rare Disease Collaborative Networks, which are embedded in NHS service specifications and underpinned by commissioned research on how best to operationalise better co-ordination of care in the NHS.

- The requirement for new and revised NHS service specifications to consider the psychosocial needs of patients, including for people with a rare disease.⁷
- The Children and Young People’s Transformation Programme, which is developing a framework to improve experiences from child to adult care.⁷
- The revised NICE quality standard on how transition from children’s to adults’ services can be made relevant to the needs of the rare diseases community.²¹
- Pilot testing of two SWAN (Syndrome Without A Name) clinics in England, one for children and one for adults, drawing on experience of SWAN clinics in Wales.⁷
- The Generation Study, which tests newborns for over 200 rare diseases with a view to improving the early identification of rare disease (<https://www.generationstudy.co.uk/>).

There is also a need to address dismissive attitudes towards certain groups with rare diseases, including women, ethnic minorities and children. This may require interventions not limited to people with a rare disease, which tackle attitudes which undermine the experiences of these groups more broadly. Additionally, it is important to consider how differences in place of residence and socioeconomic status can affect the experience of diagnosis and access to services, and specific challenges faced by people with a disability.

How did we get these findings?

We carried out a scoping review to identify and summarise the extent of evidence on inequities experienced by the rare disease community, as set out in our research aim. This involved developing a protocol which set out the aims, objectives, inclusion criteria and methods, which was prospectively registered on the Open Research Exeter (ORE) repository.²² We searched for studies using a variety of systematic search methods, and used a rigorous screening process to identify which studies met our inclusion criteria. We then extracted relevant data from the identified studies, including study characteristics and evidence of inequity. The data was then tabulated and narratively summarised in this report.

Background

Rare diseases are diseases which affect fewer than 1 in 2000 people.² Although rare diseases are individually rare, including some which are documented to affect only a handful of people worldwide, they are collectively common, with around 3.5 million people in the UK (c. 5% of the population) affected by one of 7000 documented rare diseases.⁷ Rare diseases are often life-limiting and disproportionately affect children. Seventy-five percent of rare diseases start in childhood, and around 30% of children with a rare disease die before reaching five years of age.²

Globally, people living with a rare disease can find it difficult to access appropriate care.²³ A recent report found that, in the UK, this can arise due to factors such as limited knowledge of rare diseases amongst healthcare professionals, poorly coordinated care, and scarcity of specialist centres for some conditions.²⁴ People with rare diseases can also experience delayed diagnosis, leading to months or years spent with deteriorating health without receiving appropriate treatment.²⁴ These barriers to accessing care are likely to lead to worse health outcomes for people with rare diseases than in the general population who do not encounter these barriers; and, may also lead to differences in health outcome within the rare disease community, e.g. where resources are unevenly distributed regionally.²³ Differences in health outcomes which are due to wider determinants of health (i.e. non-medical factors such ethnicity, gender and socioeconomic status) are important to address in order to ensure that all people have equal access to appropriate care.²⁵ Where people do not have equal access to appropriate care this can lead to health inequity, which is defined in this report as systemic, avoidable and unfair differences in health outcomes between populations or population subgroups.⁴

The England Rare Disease Action Plans are committed to addressing health inequities associated with rare diseases.⁵⁻⁷ This builds on the UK Rare Diseases Framework, which commits to addressing health inequalities and sets out four priorities including: (1) ensuring patients get the right diagnosis faster; (2) increasing awareness of rare diseases among healthcare professionals; (3) better coordination of care; and (4) improving access to specialist care, treatments and drugs.² In particular, the England 2023 Rare Disease Action Plan commits to gathering the evidence needed to evaluate whether rare diseases should be incorporated into the PLUS category of NHS England's Core20PLUS5 framework, enabling integrated care systems (ICS) to develop targeted actions to reduce inequalities. ICSs were developed to improve care for people with complex and long-term conditions, such as the rare disease community.²⁶ The Core20PLUS5 framework aims to support ICSs to reduce health inequities for people with complex and long-term conditions at a local and national level – the 'PLUS' category refers to population groups that are likely to experience poorer than

average health access, outcomes or experiences. These people require support from a range of different clinicians who are situated across primary, secondary and specialist care settings which requires effective co-ordination to meet their needs.²⁷ ICSs bring together NHS organisations, social care, local authorities and the voluntary and charitable sectors to collaborate on providing effective and equitable care.

Although there are well documented examples of health inequity in the rare disease community, there is limited overall understanding of the extent of the evidence in published (e.g. academic journal articles) and grey literature (i.e. literature not controlled by commercial publishers, such as reports published by charities) formats.²⁸ This includes whether there is evidence of health inequity within the rare disease community, and also between the rare disease community and the general population. As noted above, health inequities may be experienced with respect to obtaining a diagnosis and, subsequently, accessing appropriate services.²

Research question, aim and objectives

Research question

What are the key characteristics and extent of evidence on health inequities experienced within the rare disease community or between the rare disease community and the general population with regards to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services?

Aim

To identify and summarise evidence on health inequities experienced within the rare disease community or between the rare disease community and general population with regards to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services.

Objectives

1. To carry out a scoping review which will systematically identify and describe the available evidence on health inequities experienced within the rare disease community or between the rare disease community and general population with regards to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services.
2. To draw out findings relevant to the UK context.

Summary of methods

- In this section we summarise in brief the methods we used to carry out this scoping review. The methods in full are reported in Appendix A.

- We selected a scoping review methodology to address our aim and objectives as an appropriate way to identify and summarise the extent of evidence on inequities experienced by the rare disease community, as set out in the research question. Scoping reviews aim to “systematically identify and map the breadth of evidence available on a particular topic...often irrespective of source (i.e., primary research, reviews, non-empirical evidence) within or across particular contexts.”²⁹
- We followed established guidance on how to carry out scoping reviews³⁰ and the PRISMA reporting guidance for scoping reviews.³¹
- A protocol was prospectively registered on ORE.²²

Searching, study selection and inclusion criteria

We searched for relevant studies to include in our review using a combination of bibliographic databases, checking reference lists, forward citation searches, inspecting relevant journal contents pages, searching relevant websites, inspecting the included studies of relevant systematic reviews, and expert solicitation. The MEDLINE bibliographic database search is reproduced in Appendix B and the number of results for all bibliographic databases searched are detailed in Appendix C. All studies identified via these methods were inspected by two independent reviewers who coded each study as either relevant or not relevant. The studies were assessed using the inclusion criteria in Box 1. Where there were disagreements about which studies to include, these were resolved through discussion, sometimes with input from a third reviewer to help resolve disagreements.

Box 1. Inclusion criteria

Population

- Studies involving people living with a rare disease and carers of people living with a rare disease were included. We included carers to get the perspectives of people who are closely supporting people with a rare disease in the receipt of a diagnosis and accessing services.
- A rare disease was defined as a disease affecting fewer than one in 2000 people.² Rare cancers and infectious diseases were excluded.

Phenomenon of interest

- Experiences of inequity relating to receipt of a diagnosis or access to services, including:
 - Experiences of inequity which occur across the rare disease community as a whole, including (but not limited to):
 - Lack of information provision;
 - Lack of knowledge amongst clinicians;

- Delayed diagnosis.
- Experiences of inequity as these relate to characteristics which stratify health opportunities and outcomes, including (but not limited to) the following characteristics set out in the PROGRESS+ framework:⁸
 - Place of residence
 - Race/ethnicity
 - Occupation
 - Gender
 - Religion
 - Education
 - Socioeconomic status
 - Social capital
 - Age
 - Disability

Context

- The context for diagnosis or service access could include:
 - Primary, secondary and tertiary health care settings;
 - Social care settings.

Study type, geographic, date and language criteria

- We also applied the following criteria:
 - Primary studies were included if they were carried out in the UK;
 - Systematic reviews were included if they met the Database of Abstracts of Reviews of Effects (DARE) criteria³² and reported data from at least one World Bank high-income country;³²
 - Only studies/systematic reviews published in 2010 or later were included;
 - Only studies/systematic reviews published in English language were included.

We included only UK primary studies to meet the objective of drawing out findings relevant to the UK context. We supplemented this with systematic reviews which were not limited to a UK context to provide wider context from the international literature. A 2010 date limit was applied to identify literature which is relevant to the contemporary context.

Charting the data

Key characteristics of UK primary studies and systematic reviews which met our inclusion criteria were extracted into separate data extraction forms. Data on inequity was coded as relevant to receipt of a diagnosis or access to services, and whether the inequity was shared across the rare disease community, or related to subgroups described in the PROGRESS+ framework.⁸ PROGRESS+ sets out characteristics which stratify health opportunities and outcomes.⁸ We set out the key characteristics of the PROGRESS+ framework in Box 1.⁸

For the data which related to inequities shared across the rare disease community, we also drew out where these inequities were experienced differently within the rare disease community for people with different rare diseases, or in different service settings, where the data allowed. Where the data did not allow us to make this distinction, we framed these as inequities between the rare disease community and the general population. For the data which related to inequities experienced by subgroups identified by the PROGRESS+ criteria (e.g. race/ethnicity, gender or age), we assumed that these inequities would be experienced both between the rare disease community and general population, and within the rare disease community (e.g. between ethnic minority and White British population groups with rare diseases, and between ethnic minority population groups with rare diseases and the general population without a rare disease) (see Table 1).⁸

We also note that a minority of data identified were comparative, either between the rare disease community and the general population, or within the rare disease community. Comparative data is required to show a measurable difference in the experience of diagnosis or access to services between two groups. Non-comparative data on the experiences of the rare disease community were included and framed as indicating rather than demonstrating inequity. This data is not conclusive evidence of inequities as it does not establish the degree to which there are similar experiences in the general population, or elsewhere in the rare disease community.

Patient and public involvement

The protocol for this review was discussed with the standing PPI group at the Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility, PERSPEX.²² We also convened a PPI group of four adults with lived experience of rare diseases. The group was recruited by our PPI co-ordinator, Lauren Asare, using pre-existing contacts from un-related projects with rare disease population groups, and through networking at a health research conference. This group met on 17th July 2024 to discuss preliminary findings of our review, in a meeting chaired by Lauren Asare. The group included one female and three males who resided in Cornwall, Devon, Greater London and Hampshire, and included representation from the British South Asian community in addition to White British representation. All members of the group had a

rare disease listed on the Orphanet website (<https://www.orpha.net/>). The specific disease names are not included in the report to avoid identification of the participants, who belong to communities with small numbers of people.

Presentation of findings

Key characteristics of included UK primary studies and systematic reviews

The key characteristics of the identified studies which met our inclusion criteria are presented in tabulated format and described narratively; UK primary studies and systematic reviews are presented separately.

Equity data

Data on inequities in the identified studies are described narratively. Specifically, we present the data on inequities in two separate sections:

1. Inequities with respect to receipt of a diagnosis;
2. Inequities with respect to access to services.

Within these sections, we first summarise data on experiences of inequity *shared across the rare disease community*, including:

- a) how these inequities are experienced between the rare disease community and the general population, and
- b) how these inequities are experienced within the rare disease community;

Secondly, we summarise data on experiences of inequities *which relate to subgroups within the rare disease community*, with reference to the PROGRESS+ characteristics, which can lead to inequity both between the rare disease community and the general population and within the rare disease community.⁸

Content analysis was undertaken to draw out relevant detail in the identified studies and describe how this relates to inequity.

Findings

Study identification

In total we identified 136 relevant studies, including 96 UK primary studies^{3, 11-20, 24, 33-116} and 40 systematic reviews.¹¹⁷⁻¹⁵⁶ Of these, 45 UK primary studies^{3, 11, 12, 17, 33, 34, 39, 40, 46, 49-51, 53-55, 57-60, 62-65, 68, 69,}

^{71, 72, 77, 78, 82, 83, 85, 88, 92-96, 99-102, 105, 110, 116} and 17 systematic reviews were relevant to receipt of a diagnosis,^{117-119, 121, 125, 130, 132, 134, 139, 141-143, 145, 150, 153-155} and 76 UK primary studies^{3, 13-20, 24, 33, 35-45, 47, 48, 51-}

53, 55, 56, 58-63, 66, 67, 70, 71, 73-87, 89-91, 93, 94, 97-99, 101-104, 106-115 and 37 systematic reviews were relevant to access to health and social care services.^{117, 119-131, 133-145, 147-156} As required by reporting guidance for scoping reviews,³¹ the study identification process is documented in the PRISMA flow diagram in Figure 13 and accompanying narrative summary in Appendix D.ⁱ

Key characteristics of included studies

In this section we summarise the key characteristics of the included UK primary studies and systematic reviews. The key characteristics of included UK primary studies are presented in full in Table A3 in Appendix F. The key characteristics of included systematic reviews are presented in full in Table A4 in Appendix F.

Narrative summary of key characteristics of included studies

The included UK primary studies and systematic reviews comprise 122 journal articles, 11 grey literature reports^{3, 24, 58, 59, 69, 77, 83-85, 106, 116} and three theses.^{99, 100, 135} These were published between 2010 and 2024.

The number of rare diseases reported per UK primary study and systematic review ranged from one to >450.³ Although most studies and systematic reviews reported which rare diseases were included in their findings, eight studies did not provide an exhaustive report of these (see Table A5 in Appendix G) and there were also studies which reported types of rare disease without breaking these down into subtypes, e.g. studies which reported MND but not which subtypes of MND (see Table 3). These variations in reporting of rare diseases makes it impossible to count precisely how many rare diseases are represented in the included evidence. The most frequently reported rare diseases are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Most frequently reported rare disease across primary studies and systematic reviews

Primary studies	Systematic Reviews
Diseases reported in ≥10 studies (n=number of studies)	
Motor Neuron Disease (n=14)	Motor neuron disease (n=12)
	Sickle cell disease (n=10) [†]
Diseases reported in ≥5 studies (n)	
Sickle cell disease (n=9)	Cystic fibrosis (n=7)
Cystic fibrosis (n=7) [*]	Duchenne muscular dystrophy (n=6)
Inherited bleeding disorders (n=6)	Inherited bleeding disorders (n=5)
Ataxia (n=5)	

ⁱ In addition, in appendices we also report: The number of records identified per bibliographic database in Table A1 in Appendix C; and a list of full-texts which were excluded with reasons for exclusion in Table A2 in Appendix E.

*Includes one study on cystic fibrosis diabetes
†includes one study on sickle cell anaemia

Table 3 presents a breakdown of rare diseases within studies which include multiple subtypes of a rare disease (e.g. MND) or categories of rare disease (e.g. inherited bleeding disorders). Table A5 in Appendix G presents UK Primary studies and systematic reviews which report multiple rare diseases which are not limited to subtypes or categorises of rare disease.

Table 3. Primary studies and systematic reviews which include multiple types of rare disease which are either subtypes or categorised together

Disease	Primary studies, n (systematic reviews, n)	Specific types of disease: primary studies, n (systematic reviews, n)*
Rare disease with subtypes		
Motor neurone disease	14 (12)	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (bulbar/pseudobulbar onset), 4(1); amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (limb onset), 4(1); amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (not specified), 2(6); brachial amyotrophic diplegia, 2(0); familial motor neuron disease/amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, 2(0); primary lateral sclerosis, 4(1); progressive bulbar palsy, 4(1); progressive muscular atrophy, 4(1); respiratory onset, 0(1); spinal muscular atrophy (not specified), 2(2); spinal muscular atrophy (type 1), 0(2); spinal muscular atrophy (type 2), 0(2); spinal onset, 0(1); not specified, 8(2) .
Hypermobile Ehlers-Danlos syndrome	3 (1)	Ehlers-Danlos hypermobility (type II), 0(1); Ehlers-Danlos Syndrome (type III), 2(1); fibromyalgia, 1(0); not specified, 2(0).
Epidermolysis bullosa	1 (2)	Dystrophic Epidermolysis Bullosa, 1(0); Epidermolysis bullosa simplex, 1(0); junctional Epidermolysis Bullosa, 1(0); not specified 0(2).
Ataxia	5 (0)	Fragile X, 1(0); Friedreich's ataxia, 2(0); idiopathic cerebral ataxia, 1(0); spinocerebellar ataxia (general), 1(0); spinocerebellar ataxia (type 1), 1(0); spinocerebellar ataxia (type 2), 1(0); spinocerebellar ataxia (type 6), 1(0); spinocerebellar ataxia (type 7), 1(0); spinocerebellar ataxia (type 8), 1(0); not specified, 2(0).
Rare diseases categorized together		
Childhood dementias	0 (1)	Barth syndrome; CLN3 disease; complex I deficiency; complex III deficiency; cytochrome oxidase deficiency; D-bifunctional protein deficiency; genetically determined leukoencephalopathies; Kearns-Sayre syndrome; lactic acid-anaemia and stroke-like episodes (MELAS); Leigh disease; metachromatic leukodystrophy; mitochondrial encephalomyopathy, Mucopolysaccharidosis (type I, II and III); mucopolysaccharidosis (type I, Hurler syndrome); mucopolysaccharidosis (type II, Hunter syndrome); mucopolysaccharidosis (type III, Sanfilippo syndrome); mucopolysaccharidosis (type III subtype A, subtype B, or subtype C); multiple complex deficiency; NARP syndrome; Pyruvate dehydrogenase complex deficiency; Rett syndrome ; X-linked adrenoleukodystrophy; Zellweger spectrum disorders.

Inherited bleeding disorders	6 (5)	Bernard-Soulier syndrome, 1(1); diagnosed bleeding disorder (unspecified), 1(1); factor V deficiency, 1(0); factor VII deficiency, 1(0); factor X deficiency, 1(0); factor XI deficiency, 1(0); factor XIII deficiency, 1(0); Glanzmann's disease, 3(0); haemophilia A/B, 4(5); haemophilia carriers, 0(2); immune thrombocytopenia, 1(0); other factor deficiencies, 1(0); platelet disorders-general, 3(1); platelet disorder-inherited thrombocytopenia, 1(0); thrombotic thrombocytopenia purpura, 1(0); Von Willebrand's, 3(1); not specified, 1(2).
Genetic diseases†	2 (0)	NR
Rare neurodegenerative conditions	1 (0)	Charcot Marie Tooth disease; dominantly inherited ataxia; Huntington's disease; motor neuron disease; multiple system atrophy; post-polio syndrome; progressive supranuclear palsy.
Non-cancer related rare disease	0 (1)	Huntington Disease; Telangiectasia; unspecified genetic diseases.
Rare genetic intellectual disability syndromes	1 (0)	Angelman syndrome; Cornelia de Lange syndrome; Cri du Chat syndrome.
Rare epilepsy-related disorders and intellectual disabilities	0 (1)	Dravet syndrome; Dravet syndrome/Lennox-Gastaut syndrome; tuberous sclerosis complex.
Retinal dystrophies	1 (0)	Choroideremia; cone dystrophy; cone-rod dystrophy; Leber's congenital amaurosis; Retinitis pigmentosa; retinoschisis; Sorsby fundus dystrophy; unspecified retinal or macular dystrophy.
Previously undiagnosed developmental disorders	1 (0)	Abnormal growth parameters dysmorphic features; congenital anomalies; genetic disorders with a significant impact for which the molecular basis was unknown; Neurodevelopmental disorders; unusual behavioural phenotypes.

NR=not reported; *=If not specified, subtype appears in only one study; †=these could include non-rare as well as rare conditions.

People with a rare disease were the most frequently included participants in UK primary studies:

34 (35%) reported data relating solely to people with a rare disease^{16, 19, 33, 34, 36, 37, 40-43, 46, 48, 53-55, 60, 61, 64, 67, 69, 71, 73-75, 81, 82, 92-94, 98, 100, 105, 112, 114} and 42 (44%) reported data relating to both people with a rare disease and carers.^{3, 12-15, 17, 18, 20, 24, 45, 47, 49-51, 57-59, 63, 65, 66, 70, 72, 77, 78, 83, 85, 86, 88, 89, 91, 95, 97, 99, 101, 106-111, 113, 116}

Twenty (21%) UK primary studies reported data relating solely to carers (see Figure 1).^{11, 35, 38, 39, 44, 52, 56, 62, 68, 76, 79, 80, 84, 87, 89, 96, 102-104, 115} Of the systematic reviews, 12 (30%) reported data solely from people with a rare disease,^{118, 122, 126, 129, 132, 133, 137, 144, 147, 150, 151, 154} eight (20%) reported data solely from carers^{119, 120, 134, 139, 141, 142, 146, 155} and the remaining 20 (50%) reported data from both people with a rare disease and carers (see Figure 2).^{117, 121, 123-125, 127, 128, 130, 131, 135, 136, 138, 140, 143, 145, 148, 149, 152, 153,}

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Figure 1. Population breakdown (UK primary studies)

Figure 2. Population breakdown (systematic reviews)

Adults (≥18 years of age) were the most frequently included age group in the UK primary studies:

39 (41%) included solely adults with a rare disease^{12, 13, 33, 34, 40-43, 48, 53-55, 60, 62-64, 67, 70, 71, 82, 83, 85, 86, 88-91, 93, 94, 97, 99, 100, 103, 105, 108, 110, 112-114} and 31 (32%) included both adults and children, including three which reported data from people who were transitioning from child to adult care.^{3, 14-18, 20, 37, 45, 49-52, 57-59, 61, 66, 69, 73-75, 78, 80, 81, 95, 98, 101, 104, 107, 116} Seventeen (18%) included solely children with a rare disease^{11, 19, 35,}

39, 44, 47, 56, 68, 72, 76, 79, 92, 96, 102, 106, 109, 115 and nine (9%) did not report the age of participants (see Figure 3).^{24, 36, 38, 46, 65, 77, 84, 87, 111} **The majority of systematic reviews included data from both adults and children.** Specifically, 25 (63%) included both adults and children with a rare disease,^{117, 121-129, 132, 135-138, 140, 144-146, 148, 150-152, 154, 155} four (10%) included solely adults with a rare disease^{118, 130, 147, 156} and five (12%) included solely children with a rare disease.^{120, 134, 141, 149, 153} Six (15%) systematic reviews did not report the age of participants (see Figure 4).^{119, 131, 133, 139, 142, 143}

Figure 3. Age breakdown (UK primary studies)

Figure 4. Age breakdown (systematic reviews)

Most UK primary studies reported data relating to both male and female participants (n=63, 66%). Ten (10%) reported data relating solely to female participants (which could be either people with a rare disease or carers)^{17, 34, 35, 43, 60, 75, 104, 105, 107, 112} and one (1%) reported data relating solely to males (including both people with a rare disease and carers, specifically, fathers).⁵² Twenty-two (23%) UK primary studies did not report the gender of participants.^{3, 11, 20, 24, 38, 45-47, 49, 58, 63, 67, 69, 72, 74, 77, 91, 95, 99, 101, 106, 111} **Most systematic reviews did not report the gender of participants (n=22, 55%).** One (3%) systematic review reported data relating solely to females with a rare disease¹³³ and one (3%) reported data relating solely to males with a rare disease, although also included female carers.¹²⁷

Sixteen (40%) reported data relating to both male and female people with a rare disease and/or carers.^{117, 121, 122, 125, 128-130, 134, 135, 140, 141, 146, 147, 150, 155, 156}

Twenty-three (24%) UK primary studies reported the ethnicity of participants.^{13, 15, 17, 18, 33, 37, 39-41, 46, 56, 71, 75, 79, 83, 85, 92, 96, 99, 100, 103, 107, 109} Of these, one included solely white British participants and the remainder included either solely ethnic minority participants (n=3)^{18, 37, 41} or both white British/white other and ethnic minority participants (n=19).^{13, 15, 17, 33, 39, 40, 46, 56, 71, 75, 79, 83, 85, 92, 96, 99, 103, 107, 109} **Two (5%) systematic reviews reported the ethnicity of participants,**^{129, 138} including one which reported that the majority of participants were Black.¹³⁸ Overall, participant data relating to PROGRESS+ characteristics were not frequently reported in the primary studies or systematic reviews.⁸ Four UK primary studies reported data on place of residence (4%),^{63, 76, 80, 103} 12 studies reported data on occupation (13%),^{12, 17, 18, 20, 38, 41, 43, 71, 73, 75, 100, 104} three studies reported data on religion (3%),^{79, 96, 99} ten studies reported data on education (10%),^{12, 13, 15, 17, 43, 71, 100, 103} and one study reported data on socioeconomic status (1%) (see Figure 5).⁴² Gender and age were more frequently reported than other PROGRESS+ characteristics (see above and Figure 5).⁸

Figure 5. UK primary studies reporting PROGRESS+ characteristics (n)

Qualitative studies were the most frequently occurring UK primary study design (n=50, 52%)^{11, 24, 33-35, 37, 38, 40, 41, 43, 48-50, 52-56, 58-60, 62-64, 66-68, 70, 71, 73, 78, 79, 81, 82, 87-89, 91, 93, 94, 96-101, 106, 108, 111, 113} including two case studies with qualitative data.^{34, 59} Twenty-one (22%) UK primary studies were quantitative studies^{13, 14, 16, 19, 20, 36, 42, 45, 46, 57, 61, 72, 74, 83, 84, 92, 103-105, 107, 116} and 25 (26%) were mixed methods studies which included both qualitative and quantitative data.^{3, 12, 15, 17, 18, 39, 44, 47, 51, 65, 69, 75-77, 80, 85, 86, 90, 95, 102, 109, 110, 112, 114, 115} The majority of quantitative data in the quantitative studies was derived from survey or questionnaire data (n=16, 76%).^{13, 14, 16, 20, 37, 42, 45, 57, 72, 74, 83, 84, 103-105, 107} Three studies used hospital records data,^{19, 46, 61} one study used a pre-existing genetic dataset,¹¹⁶ and one was a prospective

observational study (see Figure 6).⁹² Similarly, survey and questionnaire data was the most commonly reported quantitative data in the mixed methods studies (n=23, 92%).^{3, 12, 15, 17, 18, 39, 44, 47, 51, 65, 75-77, 80, 85, 86, 95, 102, 109, 110, 112, 114, 115} Two mixed methods studies used quantitative medical records data.^{69, 90} Of the systematic reviews, eight (20%) included solely qualitative studies,^{118, 127, 129, 130, 134, 138, 146, 154, 155} two (5%) included solely quantitative studies^{122, 136} and 30 (75%) included multiple study designs including qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods studies.^{117-121, 123-126, 128, 131-133, 135, 137, 139-145, 147-153, 156} The median number of studies included in the systematic reviews was 24.5 (range 6-59).

Figure 6. Study designs (UK primary studies)

Inequities experienced by the rare disease community

In this section we summarise the data on inequities experienced by the rare disease community as these relate to (1) receipt of a diagnosis and (2) access to services. Within these two categories we first summarise experiences *shared across the rare disease community*, including (a) how these are experienced between the rare disease community and the general population, and (b) how these are experienced within the rare disease community; and, secondly, we summarise experiences of inequities *which relate to subgroups within the rare disease community*, with reference to the PROGRESS+ characteristics,⁸ which can lead to inequity both within the rare disease community and between the rare disease community and the general population.

In summary, we identified 17 types of inequity across the 136 included studies. Of these, 11 were shared across the rare disease community and six related to subgroups within the rare disease community, as described in the PROGRESS+ framework.⁸ The different types of inequity identified within each of these categories are detailed in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively.

Table 4. Types of inequity shared across the rare disease community

Type of inequity	Description reported by people with a rare disease and their carers
Delayed diagnosis	Experiencing delays to receiving a diagnosis of a rare disease.

Lack of knowledge	Lack of knowledge about rare diseases amongst health and social care professionals which hinders diagnosis and accessing services, which can also include dismissive attitudes towards symptoms of rare diseases.
Lack of information	Health and social care professionals did not always provide or signpost people with a rare disease to relevant or sufficient information about their condition.
Limited service provision (comprising six types of inequity)	Challenges with accessing appropriate services, often related to limited services provision, but also more specific challenges within different types of services. These included mental health services, emergency services, dentistry services, specialist services, social care services and services in general where these were not specified.
Limited services for undiagnosed conditions	Specific challenges for people with symptoms of a rare disease without a diagnosis (i.e. syndrome without a name) when accessing services.
Lack of care co-ordination	Experiencing a lack of care co-ordination which adversely affects the receipt of a diagnosis and accessing services after a diagnosis is received.

Table 5. Types of inequity relating to subgroups in the rare disease community

Type of inequity	Description reported by people with a rare disease and their carers
Place of residence	Where someone lives can affect the treatment and support which they receive.
Race/ethnicity	Ethnicity can affect the treatment and support which they receive.
Gender	Gender can affect the treatment and support which they receive.
Socioeconomic status	Socioeconomic status can affect the treatment and support which they receive.
Age	Age can affect the treatment and support which they receive.
Disability	Disability can affect the treatment and support which they receive.

In the remainder of this section, we narratively summarise the key characteristics of the data relating to each type of inequity. This is organised under two main headings: (1) inequities with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and (2) inequities with respect to access to services. In addition to the narrative summary below, the different types of inequity and the number of supporting studies per type of inequity are also tabulated in Table A6 and Table A7 in Appendix H.

1. Inequities with respect to receipt of a diagnosis

Overall, 12 types of inequity were identified with respect to receipt of a diagnosis. Of these, six were experienced across the rare disease community, including four which included comparative data from within the rare disease community. An additional six types of inequity were experienced by

subgroups within the rare disease community described in the PROGRESS+ framework.⁸ These types of inequity were identified in 45 UK primary studies^{3, 11, 12, 17, 33, 34, 39, 40, 46, 49-51, 53-55, 57-60, 62-65, 68, 69, 71, 72, 77, 78, 82, 83, 85, 88, 92-96, 99-102, 105, 110, 116} and 17 systematic reviews.^{117-119, 121, 125, 130, 132, 134, 139, 141-143, 145, 150, 153-155}

1.1. Inequities shared across the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis

a) Inequities between the rare disease community and the general population

An overview of the numbers of studies indicating different types of inequity between the rare disease community and the general population with respect to receipt of a diagnosis is presented in Figure 7. The following section provides a narrative summary of the data relating to each of these inequities.

Figure 7. Inequities between the rare disease community and general population with respect to diagnosis

Delayed diagnosis

Data indicated that delays to the diagnosis of a rare disease may lead to inequity between people with a rare disease and the general population, who do not routinely experience similar delays to diagnosis. Thirty-eight studies reported experience of delayed diagnosis, including 26 UK primary studies^{3, 12, 33, 34, 39, 40, 49, 53, 54, 57-59, 62-64, 69, 71, 77, 78, 82, 83, 85, 88, 94, 100, 101} and 12 systematic reviews.^{80, 117, 119, 121, 125, 130, 134, 141, 142, 145, 154, 155} The relevant data in these studies were predominantly qualitative data or non-comparative survey data, with one systematic review reporting comparative quantitative data.¹⁴² Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to delayed diagnosis

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Alstrom syndrome (1) ⁵⁹	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹

ANCA-associated Vasculitis (1) ⁶⁹	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Ataxia and progressive ataxia (2) ^{53, 54}	MND (3) ^{119, 125, 130, 145}
Bardet Biedl Syndrome (1) ⁶⁹	Frontotemporal lobar degeneration (1) ¹⁴²
Cavernoma (1) ⁵⁹	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ¹¹⁷
Chronic intestinal pseudo-obstruction (1) ⁵⁹	Primary ciliary dyskinesia (1) ¹²¹
Cystic fibrosis (1) ¹⁰⁰	Multiple rare diseases (3: Mc Mullan 2022; von der Lippe 2017; von der Lippe 2022) ^{80, 154, 155}
Deletion on chromosome 4q (1) ⁵⁹	-
Desmoid fibromatosis (1) ⁷¹	-
Dystonia (1) ⁸²	-
Ehlers-Danlos syndrome (3) ^{39, 40, 59}	-
Guillain-Barre Syndrome (1) ³³	-
Hereditary spastic paraparesis (1) ⁶³	-
Motor neurone disease (4) ^{12, 64, 88, 94}	-
Multiple System Atrophy (2) ^{83, 85}	-
Rare genetic intellectual disabilities (1) ⁶²	-
Retinal dystrophies (1) ⁴⁹	-
Sickle cell disease (1) ⁵⁹	-
Trimethylaminuria (1) ⁵⁷	-
Tuberous sclerosis complex (2) ^{69, 78}	-
Tumour Necrosis Factor Receptor Associated Periodic Syndrome (TRAPS) (1) ³⁴	-
Multiple rare diseases (4: Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; Muir 2016; Simpson 2021) ^{3, 58, 77, 101}	-

Data in UK primary studies indicated the perception amongst people with a rare disease and their carers that clinicians often lack the requisite knowledge to make a timely diagnosis.^{40, 62-64} This could sometimes lead to misdiagnosis, which further delayed accurate diagnosis.^{3, 33, 34, 71, 85} People with a rare disease and carers also reported delays to diagnosis arising from clinicians' reluctance to label people with a rare disease,^{3, 39, 53, 54, 58, 71, 78, 82, 100} and the need for many referrals and long wait times for appointments.^{49, 58, 59, 69, 71, 88} Data in systematic reviews indicated similar experiences, including quantitative data which compared the time to diagnosis for people with frontotemporal lobar degeneration (59.2 months) and Alzheimer's disease (39.1 months), as a comparison between time to diagnosis of a rare disease and a similar disease experienced in the general population.¹⁴² Misdiagnosis was reported as a recurrent issue for those affected by frontotemporal lobar degeneration, with one study reporting that out of 19 patients with frontotemporal lobar

degeneration, only one received this diagnosis prior to referral to specialist clinic; the remaining were initially misdiagnosed with depression, manic depression, psychosis or dementia.¹⁴² In some cases, this lack of knowledge, combined with the lack of apparent and visible symptoms in some rare diseases, can lead clinicians to accuse patients of fabricating illnesses and dismissing their symptoms as unimportant or non-existent.^{117, 125, 134, 145} Patients and carers also reported not being referred to the appropriate specialists for diagnosis, or waiting long times until they were eventually referred.^{117, 121, 141, 145}

Lack of knowledge

Data indicated that health professionals' limited knowledge about rare diseases when making a diagnosis may lead to inequity between people with a rare disease and the general population. Twenty-three studies reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context, including 18 UK primary studies^{3, 11, 33, 39, 40, 49, 53, 57, 58, 62, 64, 77, 82, 88, 94, 95, 102, 110} and six systematic reviews.^{117, 132, 134, 141, 154, 155} The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to lack of knowledge and diagnosis

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Adrenal Insufficiency (1) ¹⁰²	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹
Ataxia (1) ⁵³	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ¹¹⁷
Cystic fibrosis (1) ⁵³	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (2) ^{39, 40}	MND (1) ¹³²
MND (2) ^{88, 94}	Multiple rare diseases (2: von der Lippe 2017; von der Lippe 2022) ^{154, 155}
Polyneuropathy Organomegaly Endocrinopathy Monoclonal gammopathy Skin changes (POEMS) syndrome (1) ¹¹⁰	-
Rare genetic intellectual disabilities (1) ⁶²	-
Sickle cell disease (2) ⁵³	-
Trimethylaminuria (1) ⁵⁷	-
Multiple rare disease (4: Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; Muir 2016; Peter 2022) ^{3, 58, 77, 95}	-

Data in UK primary studies indicated the perception amongst people with a rare disease and carers that clinicians had a general lack of awareness of symptoms of rare diseases,^{3, 11, 40, 53, 57, 58, 62, 68, 77, 94, 102, 110} and dismissive attitudes towards symptoms,^{39, 77, 88, 102} which sometimes led to delays to

diagnosis (see above). Dismissive attitudes included dismissiveness towards the existence of hypermobile syndromes,³⁹ dismissal from GP consultation without further investigation of symptoms of multiple rare diseases,^{77, 88} and feeling the need to “fight” for clinician acknowledgement of symptoms of adrenal insufficiency.¹⁰² Data in systematic reviews indicated similar experiences, including dismissive attitudes towards symptoms, particularly towards the existence of hypermobile syndromes.¹¹⁷ Even when a diagnosis was achieved, people with a rare disease and their carers reported dissatisfaction with the communication and accuracy of the diagnosis,¹³² and that clinicians were unwilling to address their limited knowledge of a rare condition through learning more about it, which impacted parents’ ability to access the appropriate services.¹⁴¹

Lack of information

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers may receive less information about a disease at the point of diagnosis compared to diseases experienced in the general population. Twenty-five studies reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context, including 17 UK primary studies^{3, 12, 33, 50, 51, 58, 65, 68, 72, 77, 83, 85, 88, 93-95, 100} and eight systematic reviews.^{118, 119, 130, 134, 139, 141, 143, 153} The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to lack of information and diagnosis

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Acromegaly (1) ⁹³	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹
Cystic Fibrosis (1) ¹⁰⁰	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Guillain-Barre Syndrome (1) ³³	MND including one specifically on ALS (4) ^{118, 119, 130, 143}
Lysosomal acid lipase deficiency (1) ⁶⁸	MS (1) ¹¹⁸
MND (4) ^{12, 65, 88, 94}	Multiple rare diseases (2: McMullan 2022; Tsitsani 2023) ^{139, 153}
Multiple System Atrophy (1) ^{83, 85}	-
Multiple rare diseases (5: Costa 2022; Crowe 2019; Franklish 2022; Hytiris 2021; Limb 2010; Muir 2016; Peter 2022) ^{3, 50, 51, 58, 72, 77, 95}	-

Data in UK primary studies mainly focused on information needs immediately after a diagnosis. Specifically, data indicated that people with a rare disease and carers have unanswered questions about their diagnosis,⁵⁰ and specific information needs around treatment options, services and care pathways.^{12, 51} People with a rare disease also reported challenging experiences trying to find

information on the internet after a diagnosis.⁶⁸ Similarly, most systematic reviews reported a lack of information immediately after a diagnosis. People with a rare disease felt that clinicians were unable to signpost them to reliable information sources¹¹⁸ or to adequate support, such as rare disease family groups, psychologists and social services.¹⁵³ People with a rare disease and carers also reported specific information needs relating to treatment plans,^{118, 119} prognosis^{118, 119} and caring skills.¹⁴³ One systematic review reported a lack of information during the diagnostic process, with parents reporting insufficient information around the diagnostic tests their child was undergoing.¹⁴¹

Access to services in the context of receipt of a diagnosis

Two types of service were identified as relevant to the experience of inequity between the general population and rare disease community in the context of receipt of a diagnosis: specialist services and mental health services.

Specialist services

Data on specialist services indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced limited access to specialist services when seeking diagnostic tests. Data in one study showed that people with symptoms of a rare disease perceived that primary care clinicians were reluctant to refer for them for diagnostic tests due to a proprietorial sense of their patients' care.⁵⁸ These people reported feeling they need to "fight" or "struggle" for access to services for a diagnosis.⁵⁸ Multiple rare diseases were reported in this study.⁵⁸

Mental health services

Qualitative data in one study indicated that people with symptoms of a rare disease requested access to mental health services when seeking a diagnosis, but it was either not available or there were long wait times.⁵⁸ This related to multiple rare diseases.⁵⁸ This potentially leads to inequity between the rare disease community and the general population. However, difficulty accessing mental health services is also reported in the general population.¹⁰

Lack of care co-ordination

Data indicated that people with symptoms of a rare disease and their carers experienced a lack of care co-ordination when seeking a diagnosis, which may not be experienced by the general population who do not typically have similarly complex care needs. Two mixed methods and one qualitative UK primary study reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context.^{39, 58, 65} Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Rare diseases in UK primary studies relating to care co-ordination and diagnosis

Rare diseases (studies, n)
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹

MND (1)⁶⁵

Multiple rare diseases (1: Franklish 2022)⁵⁸

Qualitative data indicated the perception that there was a lack of clarity around pathways to diagnosis, and confusion amongst both clinicians and people with a rare disease about the different clinicians involved in the diagnostic pathway.^{39, 58, 65}

b) Inequities within the rare disease community

An overview of the numbers of studies indicating how inequities shared across the rare disease community are experienced differently within the rare disease community, with respect to receipt of a diagnosis, is presented in Figure 8. The following section provides a narrative summary of the data relating to each of these inequities.

Figure 8. Inequities within the rare disease community with respect to diagnosis

Delayed diagnosis

Data indicated that delays to the diagnosis of a rare disease may lead to inequity within the rare disease community. One UK primary study reported quantitative survey data on receipt of a diagnosis in this context.¹² This study showed that people with MND experience a wide range of time to diagnosis (median 398 days; range 35 to 3348 days).¹²

Lack of knowledge

Data indicated that health professionals' limited knowledge about rare diseases when making a diagnosis may lead to inequity within the rare disease community. Quantitative survey data showed

that people with MND seen at a specialist clinic were more likely to be satisfied with their experience of diagnosis than people not seen in an MND specialist clinic.¹²

Lack of information

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers may receive differing amounts of information about their disease at the point of diagnosis, which may lead to inequity within the rare disease community. One mixed methods UK primary study reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context.¹² Quantitative survey data showed that people who receive a diagnosis of MND in neurology clinics and their carers received less than half of the information about their diagnosis recommended in NICE guidance.¹² In comparison, for people who receive a diagnosis of MND in MND specialist centres there was greater, albeit not full, compliance with the information provision recommended in NICE guidance.¹²

Access to services

Specialist services

Data in one study showed that people who were diagnosed with MND in a specialist centre were more likely to provide a high satisfaction rating than those not diagnosed at an MND specialist centre.¹² A contributing factor to this was a more frequently offered invitation for follow up discussion with a neurologist in specialist centres, compared with fewer follow up invitations for follow up discussion offered outside of specialist centres.¹²

1.2. Inequities experienced by subgroups within the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis

An overview of the numbers of studies indicating different types of inequity experienced by subgroups within the rare diseases community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis is presented in Figure 9.⁸ These types of inequity could be experienced both between the rare disease community and the general population, and within the rare disease community. The following section provides a narrative summary of the data relating to each of these inequities.

Figure 9. Inequities relating to subgroups within the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis

Place of residence

Data indicated that geographic location may impact on the experience of receipt of a diagnosis for people with a rare disease and their carers. Two UK primary studies^{58, 96} and one systematic review reported qualitative data on experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context.¹⁵³ Multiple rare disease were reported in the UK primary studies^{58, 96} and the systematic review.¹⁵³

The data indicated that people with symptoms of a rare disease face challenges in accessing services for diagnostic tests where this requires travelling to tertiary services which are far away from their home, including financial challenges with respect to cost of travel.^{58, 96, 153} This may not be experienced in the general population who do not need access to specialist services, and access may vary within the rare disease community depending on how far they live from a specialist centre.

Race/ethnicity

Data indicated that the ethnicity of people with a rare disease may impact on the experience of receipt of a diagnosis. Five UK primary studies, comprising two qualitative studies and two quantitative studies, reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context.^{46, 58, 92, 99, 116} Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Rare diseases in UK primary studies relating to race/ethnicity and diagnosis

Rare disease (studies, n)
Developmental disorders (1) ¹¹⁶
Fabry disease (1) ⁴⁶
Medium chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency (1) ⁹²

Rare neurodegenerative conditions (1) ⁹⁹
Multiple rare diseases (1: Franklish 2022) ⁵⁸

Qualitative data in two UK primary studies indicated that ethnic minority patients with symptoms of a rare disease may receive different treatment to white British patients.^{58, 99} One study reported the perception that ethnicity may be a factor in whether a patient is believed regarding their symptoms,⁵⁸ and one study reported that language may be a barrier to conveying symptoms to clinicians for some ethnic minority patients.⁹⁹ Additionally, quantitative data in three UK primary studies showed that ethnic minority patients may be less likely to receive a diagnosis of a rare disease than white British patients.^{46, 92, 116} This included Medium chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency,⁹² Fabry disease,⁴⁶ and multiple rare genomic diseases.¹¹⁶ This outcome was explained in one study, which used pre-existing genetic datasets for diagnosis, as due to limited ethnic minority representation in the datasets.¹¹⁶

Gender

Data indicated that the gender or sex of people with a rare disease or their carers may impact on the experience of receipt of a diagnosis. Seven studies reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context, including six UK primary studies^{17, 39, 58, 60, 105, 116} and one systematic review.¹⁵⁰ Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to gender and diagnosis

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Developmental disorders (1) ¹¹⁶	Inherited bleeding disorders ¹⁵⁰ (1)
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹	-
Fibrous dysplasia (1) ¹⁰⁵	-
McCune-Albright syndrome (1) ¹⁰⁵	-
Inherited bleeding disorders (1) ¹⁷	-
Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome (1) ⁶⁰	-
Multiple rare diseases (1: Franklish 2022) ⁵⁸	-

Qualitative data in four UK primary studies indicated that women perceived dismissive attitudes towards their symptoms, or the symptoms of their children, prior to diagnosis.^{17, 39, 58, 60} This included the attribution of concern about their child’s symptoms to mental ill health,³⁹ and dismissal of their symptoms as within the bounds of normal menstrual health.¹⁷ One systematic review similarly

reported dismissive attitudes towards symptoms in female patients, leading to misdiagnosis and diagnostic delay.¹⁵⁰

Additionally, quantitative survey data in one UK primary study reported that women experience a long time to diagnosis of a rare disease, specifically, fibrous dysplasia and McCune-Albright syndrome.¹⁰⁵ Similarly, one systematic review reported that women experience a longer time to diagnosis than men for bleeding disorders (14.0 ± 16.6 years vs 8.1 ± 17.0 years; $P < .001$).¹⁵⁰ Contrastingly, one UK primary study reported quantitative data that a diagnosis was less likely to be obtained for male patients (OR: 0.72, 95% CI: 0.67-0.79).¹¹⁶

Socioeconomic status

Data indicated that the financial status of people with a rare disease or carers may impact on the experience of receipt of a diagnosis. Four qualitative and one mixed methods UK primary studies reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context.^{39, 58, 88, 94, 96} Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Rare diseases in UK primary studies relating to socioeconomic status and diagnosis

Rare diseases (studies, n)
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹
Genetic diseases (1) ⁹⁶
MND (2) ^{88, 94}
Multiple rare diseases (1: Franklish 2022) ⁵⁸

Qualitative data in the UK primary studies indicated that people with symptoms of a rare disease or their carers sometimes used their financial resources to access diagnostic tests for a rare disease from private health care services.^{39, 88, 94, 96} This was carried out due to delays to the receipt of a diagnosis from NHS service providers, even if this resulted in “significant personal cost”.⁹⁴ Within the NHS, patients were sometimes signposted to diagnostic services outside of their locality which they did not have sufficient funds to travel to.⁵⁸

Age

Data indicated that the age of people with a rare disease may impact on the experience of receipt of a diagnosis. Four studies reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context, including three UK primary studies^{39, 58, 105} (including qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods studies) and one systematic review.¹⁴² Rare diseases reported are presented in Table 13.

Table 13. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to age and diagnosis

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹	Frontotemporal lobar degeneration (1) ¹⁴²
Fibrous dysplasia (1) ¹⁰⁵	-
McCune-Albright syndrome (1) ¹⁰⁵	-
Multiple rare diseases (1: Franklish 2022) ⁵⁸	-

Qualitative data in UK primary studies reported that clinicians were reluctant to give a child a diagnostic label of Ehlers-Danlos syndrome,³⁹ and that being a child could mean that clinicians are less trusting of what they say about their symptoms.⁵⁸ Additionally, quantitative survey data in one UK primary study reported that people who experience symptoms of fibrous dysplasia or McCune-Albright syndrome at a young *or* older age can have a longer time to diagnosis than people who experience symptoms in between these age groups.¹⁰⁵

Quantitative data in one systematic review reported that a diagnosis of early onset dementia is often hindered due to a lack of knowledge amongst clinicians.¹⁴²

Disability

Data indicated that disabled people may have different experiences of receipt of a diagnosis to able-bodied people. Two qualitative UK primary studies reported experiences of receipt of a diagnosis in this context.^{62, 99} Rare diseases reported in these studies included rare genetic intellectual disabilities⁶² and rare neurodegenerative conditions.⁹⁹

Qualitative data indicated the perception that symptoms of a rare disease were sometimes erroneously attributed to pre-existing disability,⁹⁹ and that there was a prejudice against diagnosing intellectual disabilities, including rare genetic intellectual disabilities.⁶²

2. Inequities with respect to access to services

Overall, 16 types of inequity were identified with respect to access to services. Of these, 10 were experienced across the rare disease community, including three which included comparative data from within the rare disease community. An additional six types of inequity were experienced by subgroups within the rare disease community described by the PROGRESS+ framework.⁸ These types of inequity were identified in 76 UK primary studies^{3, 13-20, 24, 33, 35-45, 47, 48, 51-53, 55, 56, 58-63, 66, 67, 70, 71, 73-87, 89-91, 93, 94, 97-99, 101-104, 106-115} and 37 systematic reviews.^{117, 119-131, 133-145, 147-156}

2.1. Inequities shared across the rare disease community with respect to access to services

a) Inequities between the rare disease community and the general population

An overview of the numbers of studies indicating different types of inequity between the rare disease community and the general population with respect to access to services is presented in Figure 10. The following section provides a narrative summary of the data relating to each of these inequities.

Figure 10. Inequities between rare disease community and general population with respect to access to services

Lack of knowledge

Data indicated that health professionals' limited knowledge about rare diseases may lead to inequity between people with a rare disease and the general population when accessing services. Forty-seven studies reported experiences of a lack of knowledge in this context, including 32 UK primary studies^{14, 18, 24, 33, 36-40, 44, 52, 54, 55, 58, 62, 70, 71, 74, 76, 80-82, 85-87, 98, 102, 103, 106, 111, 112, 115} and 15 systematic reviews.^{125-127, 130, 134, 138, 139, 141, 143, 145, 147, 151, 153-155} The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 14.

Table 14. Rare diseases in UK primary studies relating to lack of knowledge and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Adrenal insufficiency (1) ¹⁰²	Childhood dementias (1), ¹⁴¹
Ataxia and progressive ataxia (2) ^{14, 54}	Cystic fibrosis (1) ¹⁵¹
Desmoid fibromatosis (1) ⁷¹	DMD (1) ¹²⁷
DMD (1) ⁵²	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Dystonia (1) ⁸²	Inherited bleeding disorders, specifically haemophilia (1) ¹⁵¹

Ehlers-Danlos syndrome (2) ^{39, 40}	Juvenile Idiopathic arthritis (1) ¹⁵¹
Epidermolysis bullosa (1) ⁵⁵	MND (4) ^{125, 130, 143, 145}
Guillain-Barre syndrome (1) ³³	Nephrotic syndrome (1) ¹⁵¹
Haemophilia (1) ¹¹²	Sickle cell disease (3) ^{126, 138, 147, 151}
Huntington disease (2) ^{38, 103}	Undiagnosed condition (1) ¹⁵¹
IgA nephropathy (1) ¹¹¹	Multiple types of rare diseases (4: McMullan 2022; Tsitsani 2023; von der Lippe 2017; von der Lippe 2022) ^{139, 153-155}
Inherited bleeding disorders (2) ^{74, 76}	-
Lipoprotein lipase deficiency (1) ⁸⁶	-
Long-segment congenital tracheal stenosis (1) ¹¹⁵	-
MND (2) ^{70, 87}	-
Multiple system atrophy (1) ⁸⁵	-
Phenylketonuria (1) ⁴⁴	-
Rare intellectual disabilities (1) ⁶²	-
Sickle cell disease (5) ^{18, 36, 37, 81, 98}	-
Multiple rare diseases (4: Franklish 2022; McMullan 2022; Specialised Healthcare Alliance 2023; Spencer-Tansley 2018) ^{24, 58, 80, 106}	-

In addition to the perception that clinicians have a general lack of knowledge about rare diseases when accessing services,^{14, 18, 36-39, 44, 52, 54, 62, 70, 71, 74, 76, 80, 86, 87, 98, 102, 103, 106, 115} qualitative data from UK studies indicated the perception that clinicians dismissed symptoms that they did not understand,^{40, 55, 111} and that they accused people with symptoms of a rare disease as exaggerating the extent of their symptoms, or entirely fabricating their symptoms, which was sometimes perceived to occur due to ignorance about rare diseases.^{81, 82, 86, 111} As a result, people with a rare disease and carers felt that they were not listened to or taken seriously.^{33, 58, 81, 82} Data in systematic reviews also indicated the perception amongst people with a rare disease and carers that clinicians have a general lack of knowledge about rare diseases in the context of accessing services.^{125, 134, 141, 143, 147, 153, 154} Two systematic reviews identified that clinicians' lack of understanding meant that people with a rare disease and carers were unable to have conversations about end of life.^{127, 130} As a result, patients and their carers reported needing to educate clinicians to provide appropriate care.^{125, 134, 138, 139, 145}

Lack of information

Data on lack of information indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers may receive less information about a disease when accessing services than the general population. Thirty-four

studies reported lack of information in this context, including 22 UK primary studies^{3, 18, 20, 33, 35, 38, 40, 41, 45, 48, 56, 62, 71, 85, 86, 89, 90, 94, 106, 108, 111, 113} and 12 systematic reviews.^{125, 127, 140-143, 145, 146, 148, 152, 154, 156} The relevant data in the studies comprised of qualitative data and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 15.

Table 15. Rare diseases in UK primary studies relating to lack of information and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Cystic fibrosis (1) ⁴⁸	Childhood dementia (1) ¹⁴¹
Cystic fibrosis diabetes (1) ⁵⁶	Cystic fibrosis (1) ¹⁴⁰
Desmoid fibromatosis (1) ⁷¹	DMD (2) ^{127, 146}
DMD (1) ²⁰	Frontotemporal lobar degeneration (1) ¹⁴²
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ⁴⁰	MND (4) ^{125, 143, 145, 156}
Guillain-Barre Syndrome (1) ³³	Rare epilepsy-related disorders and intellectual disability (1) ¹⁵²
Huntington disease (1) ³⁸	Sickle cell disease (1) ¹⁴⁸
IgA Nephropathy (1) ¹¹¹	Multiple rare diseases (1: von der Lippe 2017) ¹⁵⁴
Lipoprotein lipase deficiency (1) ⁸⁶	-
MND (5) ^{89, 90, 94, 108, 113}	-
Multiple system atrophy (1) ⁸⁵	-
Rare intellectual disabilities ⁶²	-
Sickle cell disease (3) ^{18, 41, 45}	-
Undiagnosed genetic conditions (1) ³⁵	-
Multiple rare diseases (2: Muir 2016; Spencer - Tansley 2018) ^{3, 106}	-

In addition to a general unmet need for information about rare diseases from service providers,^{20, 33, 38, 40, 62, 71, 86, 89, 106, 111} data in UK primary studies indicated a need for more information about what services and treatments were available,^{3, 45, 56, 90, 94, 113} who to contact with questions about rare diseases,³⁵ more information about shielding during the COVID pandemic,^{18, 41} and information about sexual relationships.¹⁰⁸ Data in two systematic reviews indicated similar experiences, including a lack of information specifically for carers.^{142, 145} Of these, one systematic review reported quantitative survey data showing that carers of people with frontotemporal lobar degeneration are less satisfied with the information they receive than carers of people with Alzheimer’s disease, and that the information needs of frontotemporal lobar degeneration carers is higher than that of carers for people with Alzheimer’s disease.¹⁴²

Access to services

There were six types of service which were reported as relevant to the experience of inequity between the general population and rare disease community in the context of accessing services: mental health services, dental services, emergency services, specialist services, social care services and services for undiagnosed conditions. There was also data relating to service access in general, where no specific service was identifiable.

General service access

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced barriers to accessing services which were generically described as “health care” or similar, without providing more detail about specific service settings. This may lead to inequity between the rare disease community and the general population. Twenty-five studies reported data in this context, including 15 UK primary studies^{33, 39, 41, 53, 58, 62, 63, 78-80, 83, 85, 97, 110, 113} and 10 systematic reviews.^{119, 126, 127, 130, 134, 136, 141, 143, 146, 153} The relevant data comprised of qualitative data, and comparative and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported in the UK primary studies and systematic reviews are detailed in Table 16.

Table 16. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic review relating to access to services (general)

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Ataxia (1) ⁵³	Childhood dementia (1) ¹⁴¹
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹	DMD (2) ^{127, 146}
Genetic diseases (1) ⁷⁹	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Guillain-Barre syndrome (1) ³³	MND (3) ^{119, 130, 143}
Hereditary spastic paraparesis (1) ⁶³	Sickle cell disease (2) ^{126, 136}
MND (2) ^{97, 113}	Multiple rare diseases (1: Tsitsani 2023) ¹⁵³
Multiple system atrophy (2) ^{83, 85}	-
Polyneuropathy Organomegaly Endocrinopathy Monoclonal gammopathy Skin changes (POEMS) syndrome (1) ¹¹⁰	-
Sickle cell disease (1) ⁴¹	-
Rare genetic intellectual diseases (2) ⁶²	-
Tuberous sclerosis complex (1) ⁷⁸	-
Multiple rare diseases (2: Franklish 2022; McMullan 2022) ^{58, 80}	-

Data in UK primary studies indicated a general lack of service provision. This was perceived as due to budgetary constraints,⁵³ and a perceived need to “fight” or “struggle” to access services.^{62, 80} Where there was limited service provision, people with a rare disease and carers reported that they

sometimes seek care via charities³³ or private care,³⁹ and sometimes prefer to manage pain at home to avoid using NHS services which do not recognise their needs.⁴¹ Follow up care after diagnosis or discharge from secondary or tertiary services was also perceived to be lacking.^{58, 63, 78, 79, 110} Data in systematic reviews reported similar experiences. Specific issues were raised in relation to primary care services,^{136, 153} with comparative data from one systematic review highlighting how the absence of primary care for patients with sickle cell disease (particularly children), increased their risk of hospitalization and 30-day re-admission compared to patients with other chronic conditions.¹³⁶

Mental health services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced barriers to accessing mental health services. Thirty-three studies reported data on lack of access to mental health services in this context, including 24 UK primary studies^{18, 33, 40, 41, 44, 45, 47, 51, 55, 58, 60, 71, 77, 80, 83-86, 89, 102, 106, 107, 109, 113} and 9 systematic reviews.^{80, 125, 131, 137, 141, 151-154} The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative data and comparative and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 17.

Table 17. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to access to services (mental health)

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
22q11 deletion syndrome (1) ⁴⁷	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹
Adrenal Insufficiency (1) ¹⁰²	Cystic fibrosis (1) ¹⁵¹
Desmoid fibromatosis (1) ⁷¹	Inherited bleeding disorders, specifically haemophilia (1) ¹⁵¹
DMD (1) ¹⁰⁹	Juvenile idiopathic arthritis (2) ^{137, 151}
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ⁴⁰	MND (2) ^{125, 131}
Epidermolysis Bullosa (1) ⁵⁵	Muscular dystrophies (1) ¹³⁷
Guillain-Barre Syndrome (1) ³³	Nephrotic syndrome (1) ¹⁵¹
Lipoprotein lipase deficiency (1) ⁸⁶	Rare epilepsy related disorders (1) ¹⁵²
Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome (1) ⁶⁰	Rare intellectual disabilities (1) ¹⁵²
MND (2) ^{89, 113}	Rare or undiagnosed condition (not specified) (1) ¹⁵¹
Multiple system atrophy (3) ⁸³⁻⁸⁵	Sickle cell disease (1) ¹⁵¹
Phenylketonuria (1) ⁴⁴	Spina bifida (1) ¹³⁷
Sickle cell disease (3) ^{18, 41, 45}	Multiple rare diseases (3: McMullan 2022; Tsitsani 2023; von der Lippe 2017) ^{80, 153, 154}
Multiple rare diseases (5: Crowe 2019; Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; McMullan 2022; Spencer-Tansley 2018) ^{51, 58, 77, 80, 106}	-

Data in UK primary studies indicated a general lack of psychological support to help with the mental health impact of coping with a rare disease diagnosis. In particular, data in qualitative studies indicated the perception that clinicians do not consider the mental health impact of living with a rare disease,^{18, 40, 41, 55, 58} including for carers;^{85, 113} and the perception that, when clinicians try to organise counselling, the waiting times are very long (in one study a 7 month waiting list was reported)³³ or it is not available, or that equivalent counselling services are available for more common diseases such as cancer.⁸⁹ Survey data showed that a minority of people with a rare disease had access to mental health support^{44, 45, 83, 85, 89, 109} or sufficient mental health support.⁷⁷ Systematic reviews reported similar experiences, including the perception that carers are offered insufficient psychological support on caring for someone with a rare disease.^{141, 152}

These experiences potentially lead to inequity between the rare disease community and the general population, albeit difficulty accessing mental health services is also reported in the general population.¹⁰ However, quantitative data in one UK primary study¹⁰⁹ and several systematic reviews^{121, 125, 137, 141, 142, 144, 150} showed that levels of anxiety, depression and stress are higher in the rare disease community than in the general population, potentially indicating greater need for mental health services.

Dental services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and carers experienced barriers to accessing dental services. Specifically, quantitative survey data in two UK primary studies indicated that people with rare inherited bleeding disorders find it difficult to find a dentist due to dental surgeries not accepting patients with a bleeding disorder.^{42, 74} Both studies reported data relating to dental services in primary health care settings.^{42, 74}

Emergency services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and carers experienced barriers to accessing appropriate care in emergency services. Three studies reported data relating to access to emergency services, including two UK primary studies^{45, 98} and one systematic review which reported comparative survey data.¹²⁶ All studies reported data relating to people with sickle cell disease. Specifically, qualitative and quantitative survey data in UK primary studies indicated that people with sickle cell disease perceived delays to receiving appropriate pain management in emergency service settings.^{45, 98} Systematic review data indicated similar experiences of pain management in emergency settings, including that sickle cell patients waited 25% longer than the general population and 50% longer than those with long bone fractures.¹²⁶

Specialist services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced barriers to accessing specialist services. Eleven studies reported data on access to specialist services, including nine UK primary studies^{3, 14-16, 38, 58, 77, 93, 114} and two systematic reviews.^{117, 134} Data in these studies comprised of qualitative data and non-comparative survey data. The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative data and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 18.

Table 18. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to access to services (specialists)

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Acromegaly (1) ⁹³	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ¹¹⁷
Ataxia and progressive ataxia (2) ^{14, 16}	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Cystic fibrosis (1) ¹¹⁴	-
Huntington disease (1) ³⁸	-
Multiple rare diseases (4: Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; Morris 2022; Muir 2016) ^{3, 15, 58, 77}	-

Qualitative data in UK primary studies indicated that there were people with a rare disease who did not have access to specialist centres. Sometimes they were not aware of specialist centres for their condition,^{3, 77} and sometimes there were significant delays to referral to specialist centres.⁵⁸ These studies did not explicitly mention distance to travel due to place of residence as a reason why they did not have access (see *Place of residence*, below). Similarly, quantitative survey data reported that a minority of people with a rare disease had access to specialist services.^{3, 14-16} Data in systematic reviews also indicated limited availability of specialist services.^{117, 134}

Social care services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced barriers to accessing social care. Seventeen studies reported data relating to access to social care services in this context, including 12 UK primary studies^{33, 47, 51, 58, 62, 77, 78, 85, 90, 91, 101, 103} and five systematic reviews.^{124, 125, 131, 142, 154} The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative data and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 19.

Table 19. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to access to services (social care)

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
22q11 deletion syndrome (1) ⁴⁷	Frontotemporal lobar degeneration (1) ¹⁴²
Guillain-Barre Syndrome (1) ³³	Huntington disease (1) ¹²⁴
Huntington disease (1) ¹⁰³	MND (2) ^{125, 132}

MND (2) ^{90, 91}	Multiple rare diseases (1: von der Lippe 2017) ¹⁵⁴
Multiple system atrophy (1) ⁸⁵	-
Rare intellectual disabilities (1) ⁶²	-
Tuberous sclerosis complex (1) ⁷⁸	-
Multiple rare diseases (4: Crowe 2019; Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; Simpson 2021) ^{51, 58, 77, 101}	-

Qualitative and quantitative survey data in UK primary studies indicated that people with rare diseases wait a long time for access to social care services,^{47, 51, 78} and are sometimes refused services after long periods of needs assessment.⁵⁸ It was also indicated that social care workers are not familiar with rare diseases, and that there is sometimes a high turnover of staff, which can impact on the quality of care.^{62, 90, 91, 103} Systematic review data indicated similar experiences, including refusal of services,^{142, 154} lack of awareness of rare diseases amongst social care workers¹²⁴ and need for specific services for young people.¹²⁵

Services for undiagnosed conditions

Data on access to services for people with undiagnosed rare diseases indicated that people with symptoms of a rare disease but no diagnosis experienced barriers to accessing services. Two UK primary studies, including one qualitative study and one mixed methods study with quantitative survey data, reported data in this context.^{3, 35} Data indicated that people with rare undiagnosed conditions perceived that services were unavailable or they did not know what services were available.^{3, 35}

Lack of care co-ordination

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced a lack of care co-ordination when accessing services. Twenty-nine studies reported data on lack of care co-ordination in this context, including 19 UK primary studies^{3, 13, 15, 35, 37, 39, 44, 58, 59, 63, 67, 71, 77, 85, 97, 101, 106, 110, 113} and ten systematic reviews.^{117, 120, 125, 139, 141, 143, 146, 153-155} The relevant data in these studies comprised of qualitative data and non-comparative survey data. Rare diseases reported in the UK primary studies and systematic reviews are detailed in Table 20.

Table 20. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to lack of care coordination and access to services.

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Alstrom syndrome (1) ⁵⁹	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹
Chronic intestinal pseudo-obstruction (1) ⁵⁹	Duchenne's Muscular Dystrophy (1) ¹⁴⁶
Deletion on chromosome 4q (1) ⁵⁹	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ¹¹⁷

Desmoid fibromatosis (1) ⁷¹	MND (2) ^{125, 143}
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (2) ^{39, 59}	Multiple rare diseases (5: Assalone 2024; McMullan 2022; Tsitsani 2023; von der Lippe 2017; von der Lippe 2022) ^{120, 139, 153-155}
Hereditary spastic paraparesis (1) ⁶³	-
MND (3) ^{67, 97, 113}	-
Multiple system atrophy (1) ⁸⁵	-
Phenylketonuria (1) ⁴⁴	-
Polyneuropathy Organomegaly Endocrinopathy Monoclonal gammopathy Skin changes (POEMS) syndrome (1) ¹¹⁰	-
Sickle cell disease (2) ^{37, 59}	-
Undiagnosed genetic conditions (1) ³⁵	-
Studies which included multiple rare diseases (7: Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; Morris 2022; Muir 2016; Simpson 2021; Spencer-Tansley 2018; Walton 2023) ^{3, 13, 15, 58, 77, 101, 106}	-

Of the UK primary studies, fifteen reported data relating to care co-ordination within health care services, including with respect to primary, secondary and tertiary services,^{3, 13, 15, 35, 37, 39, 44, 58, 59, 63, 67, 71, 77, 85, 97, 106} and four studies reported data relating to care co-ordination between health and social care settings.^{85, 102, 110, 113} Of the systematic reviews, seven reported data relating to care co-ordination within health care settings, including with respect to primary, secondary and tertiary services;^{117, 139, 141, 143, 146, 153, 155} and three systematic reviews reported data relating to care co-ordination between health and social care settings.^{120, 125, 154}

Data in UK primary studies indicated that people with a rare disease required multidisciplinary care which was perceived as lacking in coordination.^{3, 15, 35, 37, 44, 67, 77, 97, 101} This sometimes meant that people with a rare disease or their carers were required to take on a co-ordinating role themselves, communicating information between different clinicians, and arranging multiple appointments at suitable times.^{3, 35, 58, 59, 85} Data in systematic reviews reported similar experiences, with reference to “fragmented care” and health professionals working in “silos”.^{117, 155}

b) Inequities within the rare disease community

An overview of the numbers of studies indicating how inequities shared across the rare disease community are experienced differently within the rare disease community, with respect to access to

services, is presented in Figure 11. The following section provides a narrative summary of the data relating to each of these inequities.

Figure 11. Inequities within the rare disease community with respect to access to services

Access to services

There were three service types reported as relevant to the experience of inequity within the rare disease community in the context of accessing services: mental health services, specialist services and services for undiagnosed conditions.

Mental health services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease and their carers experienced barriers to accessing mental health services. One UK primary study reporting quantitative survey data found that, in a sample of 588 people with rare diseases who had accessed mental health services, 7% had accessed it through a specialist clinic (41/588) compared with 48% who had been referred by their GP (280/588) and 21% by clinicians at their hospital (123/588).¹⁰⁷ This difference in referrals to mental health services may lead to inequity within the rare disease community.

Access to specialist services

Data indicated that people with a rare disease may experience differences in access to specialist services. Quantitative survey data in one UK primary study indicated that people with ataxia with access to specialist ataxia centres had increased contact with a variety of different specialists (not limited to neurologists) compared with people with ataxia who were unable to access specialist ataxia centres.¹⁶ Furthermore, several UK primary studies reported quantitative survey data showing that a minority of people with a rare disease had access to specialist centres.¹³⁻¹⁶ Rare diseases

reported in these studies included ataxia^{14, 16} and multiple rare diseases. This variation in access to specialist centres may lead to inequity within the rare disease community.^{13, 15}

Services for undiagnosed conditions

Data on access to services for people with undiagnosed conditions indicated that people with symptoms of a rare disease, but no diagnosis, experienced barriers to accessing services. The data indicated that people with rare undiagnosed conditions perceived that services were unavailable or did not know what services were available.^{3, 35} There were two UK primary studies in this category.^{3, 35} This may lead to inequities within the rare disease community, where a rare disease has no existing diagnostic label and people are uncertain about what services are available to support them.

2.2. Inequities experienced by subgroups within the rare disease community with respect to access to services

An overview of the numbers of studies indicating different types of inequity experienced by subgroups within the rare diseases community with respect to access to services is presented in Figure 12.⁸ These types of inequity could be experienced both between the rare disease community and the general population, and within the rare disease community. The following section provides a narrative summary of the data relating to each of these inequities.

Figure 12. Inequities relating to subgroups within the rare disease community with respect to access to services

Place of residence

Data on place of residence indicated that geographic location may impact on the experience of accessing services for people with a rare disease or their carers. There were 23 studies which reported data relating to place of residence in this context, including 17 UK primary studies^{3, 14, 16, 19,}

20, 24, 35, 61, 63, 77, 85, 89, 90, 99, 102, 103, 106 and six systematic reviews.^{122, 123, 135, 136, 148, 150} Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 21.

Table 21. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to place of residence and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic review (n)
Adrenal Insufficiency (1) ¹⁰²	Bleeding disorders (1) ¹⁵⁰
Ataxia and progressive ataxias (2) ^{14, 16}	Sickle cell disease (4) ^{122, 135, 136, 148}
Congenital adrenal hyperplasia (1) ⁶¹	Multiple non-cancer related rare diseases (1; Best 2022) ¹²³
DMD (1) ²⁰	-
Hereditary spastic paraparesis (1) ⁶³	-
Huntington's disease (1) ¹⁰³	-
MND, including specifically ALS (2) ^{89, 91}	-
Multiple system atrophy (1) ⁸⁵	-
Osteogenesis imperfecta (1) ¹⁹	-
Rare neurodegenerative conditions (1) ⁹⁹	-
Undiagnosed genetic conditions (1) ³⁵	-
Multiple rare diseases, including rare neurodegenerative conditions (5: Franklish 2022; Limb 2010; Muir 2016; Specialised Healthcare Alliance 2023; Spencer-Tansley 2018) ^{3, 24, 58, 77, 106}	-

Qualitative data in UK primary studies showed that people with a rare disease and their carers need to travel long distances to access specialist services.^{24, 35, 63, 91, 102, 106, 123} This was identified as particularly challenging for people in rural areas, as the specialist centres were typically located in large urban areas.⁶³ Data also suggested that services varied between locations, leading to different standards of care depending on place of residence.^{77, 89, 99} Systematic review evidence identified additional challenges for those living in rural areas who relied on public transport to access services.¹²³

Additionally, quantitative survey data identified in UK primary studies showed that people living with a rare disease and their carers who had to travel long distances to access services were less likely to attend clinics than those living nearer,^{19, 20} and were more likely to drop out of treatment plans.⁶¹ This was shown to adversely affect other equity related experiences, for example, people who were unable to attend clinics due to distance were also less satisfied with the information they had access to.²⁰ Data also indicated that people living with a rare disease in the UK may have less access to

services than people living in other European countries.^{14, 16} One study reporting quantitative survey data found that people with Huntington’s disease in the UK were more likely to report dissatisfaction with clinicians’ knowledge than people with a rare disease in the USA (UK = 82.6% and US = 64.3%).¹⁰³

Quantitative data identified in systematic reviews also reported that people living further away from specialist centres were less likely to attend than people living nearer.^{122, 135, 136}

Race/ethnicity

Data on ethnicity indicated that the ethnicity of people with a rare disease may impact on their experience of accessing services. Nine studies reported data related to ethnicity in this context, including three UK primary studies^{18, 41, 99} and six systematic reviews.^{126, 136, 138, 144, 148, 149} Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 22.

Table 22. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to race/ethnicity and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Sickle cell disease (2) ^{18, 41}	Sickle cell disease (6) ^{126, 136, 138, 144, 148, 149}
Multiple rare neurodegenerative conditions (1) ⁹⁹	-

Qualitative data in one UK primary study indicated that sickle cell patients thought there was a link between their ethnicity and health professionals’ dismissive attitudes towards how much pain they experienced.¹⁸ Furthermore, one study reported that, during the COVID19 pandemic, sickle cell patients felt that they were sometimes not treated as vulnerable due to their ethnicity.⁴¹ Systematic reviews also indicated that people living with sickle cell disease felt stigmatized when accessing health care services, and the perception that stigmatization can impact the amount of funding which is allocated to research on sickle cell disease.^{138, 148, 149} One systematic review reported the perception that people living with sickle cell disease experience delays to accessing health care due to their ethnicity.¹³⁶

Amongst people with rare neurodegenerative disorders, not speaking fluent English was identified as a barrier to accessing services.⁹⁹

Gender

Data indicated that the gender of people with a rare disease or carers may impact on the experience of accessing services. Twelve studies reported data on gender in this context, including seven UK primary studies^{17, 39, 43, 60, 75, 108, 112} and five systematic reviews.^{117, 133, 140, 147, 150} Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 23.

Table 23. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to gender and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
Cystic fibrosis (1) ⁴³	Cystic fibrosis (2) ^{133, 140}
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ¹¹⁷
Inherited bleeding disorders (3) ^{17, 75, 112}	Inherited bleeding disorders (1) ¹⁵⁰
Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome (1) ⁶⁰	Sickle cell disease (1) ¹⁴⁷
MND (1) ¹⁰⁸	-

Qualitative data in UK primary studies indicated that women with a rare disease sometimes felt dismissed by clinicians.^{17, 39, 60} This included the perception that their concerns about symptoms were dismissed as related to mental illness,³⁹ and the perception that there is a power imbalance between the patient and doctor which leads to feeling “pushed away” from accessing appropriate health care.⁶⁰ Qualitative UK primary studies also reported that women with a rare disease perceive a lack of support for issues relating to sexual and reproductive health, including that sexual and reproductive health is rarely discussed by clinicians, and a lack of knowledge amongst clinicians on managing pregnancy.^{43, 108} Similarly, qualitative data in systematic reviews indicated that women with a rare disease perceive that women’s health is trivialised by some doctors.¹⁵⁰ It was also indicated that women’s health can be discomfoting to discuss for both patients and clinicians, which leads to lack of open communication,¹⁴⁰ and there was a perceived lack of support for issues relating to sexual and reproductive health.^{117, 133, 147}

Additionally, quantitative survey data in one UK primary study reported that one third of women patients with menorrhagia, who also have a rare bleeding disorder, do not feel that they are supplied with sufficient information.⁷⁵ Quantitative survey data in UK studies also reported that there was a large divide between the level of knowledge in specialist clinicians and primary care clinicians, which can lead to substandard care for women not registered with specialist centres.¹¹²

Socioeconomic status

Data indicated that the financial status of people with a rare disease or carers may impact on the experience of accessing services. Thirteen studies reported experiences of the impact of financial issues in this context, including five UK primary studies^{15, 39, 58, 76, 103} and eight systematic reviews.^{117, 123, 125, 135, 136, 141, 148, 156} Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 24.

Table 24. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to socioeconomic status and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
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Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ³⁹	ALS (1) ¹⁵⁶
Huntington disease (1) ¹⁰³	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹
Inherited bleeding disorders (1) ⁷⁶	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (1) ¹¹⁷
Multiple rare diseases (2: Morris 2022, Franklish 2022) ^{15, 58}	MND (2) ^{125, 156}
-	Sickle cell disease (3) ^{135, 136, 148}
-	Multiple non-cancer related rare diseases (1) ¹²³

Of the UK primary studies, all reported data relating to accessing private health or social care.^{15, 39, 76, 103} Of the systematic reviews, these included data relating to accessing health and social care in insurance-based health care systems outside the UK.^{117, 123, 125, 135, 136, 141, 148, 156}

Qualitative data in UK primary studies indicated that people with a rare disease perceived unfairness with respect to access to services due to the need to pay for private services to avoid delays to care, or to receive a better standard of care.^{15, 39} Qualitative data in systematic reviews indicated barriers to accessing health care services for people with rare diseases and carers in countries with insurance-based health care systems,^{123, 148} and financial inequities arising from costs for non-medical needs such as childcare and time out of work when accessing services for rare diseases.^{135, 141, 156} One systematic review reported that people with a rare disease in the UK use private care at great cost although do not necessarily find it helpful.¹¹⁷

Additionally, quantitative survey data in UK primary studies reported that people with a rare disease and their carers (specifically, parents) find it difficult to pay for medical care and specialist equipment.^{76, 103} One systematic review found that people living with rare diseases on low incomes in insurance-based health care systems pay higher healthcare costs and use emergency services more frequently due to lack of appropriate insurance.¹³⁶ One systematic review reported survey data showing that the cost of informal care for spinal muscular atrophy increased with the severity of disease.¹²⁵

Age

Data indicated that the age of people with a rare disease may impact on the experience of accessing services. Twenty-seven studies reported experiences of the impact of age in this context, including 15 UK primary studies^{3, 20, 39, 41, 52, 59, 66, 73, 75, 77, 81, 98, 102, 104, 106} and 12 systematic reviews.^{126-129, 134, 135, 141, 144, 148, 151-153} Rare diseases reported are detailed in Table 25.

Table 25. Rare diseases in UK primary studies and systematic reviews relating to age and access to services

UK primary studies (n)	Systematic reviews (n)
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Adrenal Insufficiency (1) ¹⁰²	Childhood dementias (1) ¹⁴¹
Alstrom syndrome (1) ⁵⁹	Cystic fibrosis (3) ^{128, 129, 151}
Cavernoma (1) ⁵⁹	DMD (1) ¹²⁷
Chronic intestinal pseudo-obstruction (1) ⁵⁹	Fragile X syndrome (1) ¹³⁴
Cystic fibrosis (1) ⁷³	Inherited bleeding disorders, specifically haemophilia (1) ¹⁵¹
Deletion on chromosome 4q (1) ⁵⁹	Juvenile idiopathic arthritis (1) ¹⁵¹
DMD (2) ^{20, 52}	Nephrotic syndrome (1) ¹⁵¹
Ehlers–Danlos syndrome (2) ^{39, 59}	Rare epilepsy-related disorders and intellectual disability (1) ¹⁵²
Menorrhagia in the context of inherited bleeding disorders (1) ⁷⁵	Rare or undiagnosed condition (not specified) (1) ¹⁵¹
Oesophageal atresia/tracheo-oesophageal fistula (1) ⁶⁶	Sickle cell disease (5) ^{126, 135, 144, 148, 151}
Sickle cell disease (4) ^{41, 59, 81, 98}	Multiple rare diseases (1: Tsitsani 2023) ¹⁵³
Tuberous sclerosis complex (1) ¹⁰⁴	-
Multiple rare diseases (3: Limb 2010; Muir 2016; Spencer-Tansley 2018) ^{3, 77, 106}	-

Qualitative data in UK primary studies reported the perception that children were treated differently to adults due to their age.^{39, 75, 98, 106} This included the perception that young people were not given appropriate pain relief due to clinicians disregarding their claims about pain,⁹⁸ and that young people were not given sufficient information about their care needs or treatment.^{75, 106} It was also perceived that children cannot access appropriate support because some specialists are only accessible in adult services.³⁹ However, with respect to transitioning between paediatric and adult care, children’s services were perceived as better than adult services, and that the transition from child to adult services is not satisfactory.^{3, 52, 59, 66, 73, 77, 102} It was also perceived that adults aged between 30 and 40 may have specific age-related needs similar to the specific needs of children or older adults but which are not catered for.^{41, 52} Systematic reviews which reported qualitative data similarly reported the perception that children’s services were better than adult services, with a similar focus on the transition from children’s to adult’s services, where this difference was felt most acutely.^{127, 128, 134, 135, 141, 144, 151} However, children and young adults also reported that their claims were sometimes dismissed or ignored by clinicians with respect to how they were treated.^{126, 129, 148}

Additionally, quantitative survey data in UK primary studies showed that adults are sometimes dissatisfied with adult rare disease services compared with children’s rare disease services.^{3, 20, 77, 104}

However, one survey, which was carried out at two time points, showed that the number of adults who were dissatisfied with adult rare disease services compared with children's rare disease services had decreased from 30% to 16% between 2010 and 2016.^{3, 77}

Disability

Data indicated that people with a rare disease who also have disabilities may have different experiences of accessing services to able-bodied people. Three UK primary studies reported experiences of the impact of disability in this context.^{62, 85, 87} Rare diseases reported in these studies included MND,⁸⁷ multiple system atrophy⁸⁵ and rare genetic intellectual disabilities.⁶²

Data indicated that carers perceive that clinicians lack understanding of people with a rare intellectual disability, which impacts on accessing services.⁶² Data also indicated that carers of people with MND who are unable to meet their own basic needs due to disability were dissatisfied with the level of care whilst staying in hospital.⁸⁷ Also, mobility problems experienced by people with multiple system atrophy were identified as leading to challenges when accessing services.⁸⁵

Discussion

This scoping review provides a summary of evidence relating to inequities experienced by the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services. In particular, the review focuses on evidence from UK settings which is reported in UK-based primary studies, but also includes evidence from systematic reviews which included primary studies from World Bank high-income countries. Overall, the review shows that the rare disease community's experiences of receipt of a diagnosis and access to health and social care services are indicative of inequities compared with the general population and within the rare disease community itself. Because much of the identified data were not comparative, for some types of inequity the review has only been able to draw attention to the reported experiences of people with a rare disease and their carers, rather than substantiate this with data which provides a quantitative or qualitative comparison between the rare disease community and general population, or within the rare disease community. However, there were some comparative data, mainly in the form of survey data, which gives a stronger indication of inequity. In this section, we summarise some of the key findings, and the strengths and limitations, of the review. We also summarise the discussion we undertook with the PPI group formed for this review.

Receipt of a diagnosis and access to services: differences and similarities

Inequities relating to receipt of a diagnosis and access to services were in many ways similar: both were predominantly supported by data on lack of knowledge and lack of information, and both were

supported by data on lack of care co-ordination. Furthermore, subgroups experiencing inequities within the rare disease community were also similar across receipt of a diagnosis and access to services, relating to place of residence, race/ethnicity, gender, socioeconomic status, age and disability. Not surprisingly, data relating to service access more frequently related to access to services than receipt of a diagnosis, but were also identified in relation to the latter, including access to specialist and mental health services. Overall, there was more data supporting inequities relating to accessing services than receipt of a diagnosis, although data relating to both types of inequities were clearly identifiable, albeit sometimes only indicated by non-comparative data.

Inequities shared across the rare disease community

Most of the evidence indicating inequities shared across the rare disease community related to the experiences of the rare disease community compared with the general population. This included experiences of delayed diagnosis, often related to lack of knowledge of rare diseases amongst clinicians, experiences of lack of information provision, and experiences of lack of care coordination for patients with complex needs. Experiences of a lack of appropriate services across a range of different services were also, collectively, frequently reported. These experiences were shared amongst people with different types of rare diseases, based on UK data, and often corroborated in the international literature in systematic reviews, albeit some rare diseases occurred more frequently in the studies than others. In particular, almost all the inequities associated with diagnosis were supported with data from UK studies relating to MND; and studies on both MND and sickle cell disease were similarly prevalent amongst data on access to services. It is perhaps not surprising that these relatively common rare diseases are more prevalent in the identified studies, which may be partly due to them attracting more UK-based funding for research than less common rare diseases.¹⁵⁷

Although much of the data which were used to identify potential inequities between the rare disease community and general population were not comparative, it was sometimes apparent that the experiences were likely to be unique or relatively specific to the rare disease community. For example, the experience of lack of knowledge of rare diseases amongst clinicians is unlikely to be experienced by the general population with respect to more common diseases, which are likely to be better understood by clinicians.¹⁵⁸⁻¹⁶⁰ Relatedly, the experiences of delayed diagnosis may be exacerbated for the rare disease community compared with the general population due to lack of knowledge amongst clinicians. (There is also a possibility that the length of time to diagnosis for some rare diseases may relate to the need to exclude more common conditions first, and thus this may be attributable in some cases to the recommended diagnostic pathway). Similarly, experiences

of a lack of information provision may relate to the limited demand for information about rare diseases compared with diseases which are more commonly experienced by the general population.

There was also evidence of experiences amongst the rare disease community which may also be experienced by others in the general population. Lack of care co-ordination, for example, may be experienced by others in the general population with complex needs.⁹ Of the several types of services which were identified in the research as providing limited access, mental health services in the UK in particular is one where people in the general population also report limited access.¹⁰ We included evidence relating to these experiences as indicating inequities in order to be inclusive of all the potentially relevant data that was identified. However, these findings should be interpreted more cautiously within the wider context of service access for the general population. With respect to mental health services, we were able to identify survey data in the included studies showing that people with rare diseases have greater mental health needs than the general population, potentially indicating increased need for services.

The relatively limited amount of evidence on how inequities shared across the rare disease community were experienced differently within the rare disease community is due to the lack of comparative data. Whilst, as noted above, it may be reasonable to assume based on non-comparative data that the characteristics of rare diseases lead to inequities between the rare disease community and general population, it is harder to ascertain this within the rare disease community without explicitly comparative data. For example, although collectively it was clear that across many different rare diseases people experienced that clinicians were lacking in knowledge, there were relatively few studies which measured or compared the experience of lack of knowledge between or within different rare disease communities. However, some studies, including UK-based studies, did report comparative data within the rare disease community. With respect to receipt of a diagnosis, comparative data showed greater satisfaction of clinician knowledge in specialist centres when receiving a diagnosis of cystic fibrosis, MND and sickle cell disease,^{11, 12} and greater satisfaction of the information provided by specialist centres when receiving a diagnosis (specifically, MND),¹² compared with people who did not receive their diagnosis in a specialist centre. Comparative data also showed differences in the experiences of accessing services, with a minority of people with a rare disease reporting access to a specialist service,¹³⁻¹⁶ and, perhaps surprisingly, significantly fewer referrals to mental health services from specialist services than from primary or secondary care services across a variety of rare diseases.¹⁰⁷ Although not based on comparative data, there also appeared to be people with symptoms of a rare disease but no diagnosis, perhaps due to lack of an existing diagnostic label, who were uncertain of what services were available.^{3, 35} This also suggests a

difference in experience between people with a diagnosis, or with symptoms of a relatively common rare disease, and people who find it harder to obtain a diagnosis.

Inequities relating to subgroups within the rare disease community

Evidence on inequities relating to subgroups within the rare disease community was identified in fewer studies than evidence on inequities which were shared across the rare disease community.⁸ This is perhaps not surprising, as the subgroups described in the PROGRESS+ criteria are by definition a subset of the whole. However, with the exception of age and gender, limited reporting of PROGRESS+⁸ characteristics has been documented in research on health inequities, with calls for this to be addressed to improve health inequity identification.¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶⁴

Much of the inequity data relating to subgroups within the rare disease community revealed similar experiences to inequities shared across the rare disease community, but which were intensified due to the specific characteristics of these groups.⁸ For example, experiences of lack of information, and lack of knowledge of clinicians, were reported in UK studies in connection with rare diseases which affect children (e.g. childhood dementia), women (e.g. MRKH, and, more generally, lack of knowledge relating to the impact of rare diseases on reproductive and menstrual health) and ethnic minorities (e.g. sickle cell disease). In addition, experiences of limited access to services for people with rare diseases were reported in UK studies in connection with place of residence, socioeconomic status and age. Beyond this, the data showed that PROGRESS+ characteristics could exacerbate or complicate these experiences of inequity.⁸ For example, dismissive attitudes towards the symptoms of ethnic minorities and women were reported in qualitative studies, including the perception amongst women that the symptoms of rare diseases are dismissed by clinicians as part of normal menstrual health,¹⁷ and the perception amongst ethnic minorities that they are mistrusted by clinicians when experiencing pain related to sickle cell disease.¹⁸ These examples relate to a potential lack of knowledge amongst clinicians of the symptoms of rare diseases, but *also* indicate potentially discriminatory attitudes towards subgroups within the rare disease community, which may further exacerbate inequities experienced by these groups.

In addition to potentially discriminatory attitudes amongst clinicians, there was evidence in UK studies that services for rare diseases are difficult to access due to geographical reasons, and that this could be exacerbated by socioeconomic status.^{19, 20} Challenges with accessing NHS services also meant that people sometimes paid for private health care services, but this was not an option to people with more limited financial resources.^{15, 39} Services were also perceived to be better for children than adults, and there was a particular problem with transitioning between paediatric and adult services, during which time the difference in care provision was felt acutely.^{3, 52, 59, 66, 73, 77, 102} In

these examples, structural and organisational factors relating to the provision of rare disease services negatively impact on the experience of receipt of a diagnosis and access to services. This does not, however, mean there are not challenges with children's services. Collecting data from children can be challenging, and this may lead to children being a silent majority in the assessment of rare disease services.¹⁶⁵

In some cases, comparative quantitative data was not explicit about why the difference occurred. For example, the odds of diagnosis of rare disease were lower for males in one study, but this was not explained.¹¹⁶

Patient and public involvement

Our meeting with the PERSPEX PPI group was instrumental in ensuring that our review did not solely focus on inequities related to PROGRESS+ characteristics but took note of other types of inequity.⁸ In our meeting with the rare diseases PPI group on 17th July 2024, two of four in the group reported receiving an incorrect diagnosis initially, one of which led to further tests which led to a correct diagnosis, and one of which was subsequently correctly diagnosed in an emergency situation. Another, female member of the group, was told she was "just anxious" when presenting with symptoms, which then took eight years to be diagnosed. The fourth member of the group found the diagnostic process challenging due to the intermittent nature of symptoms. Once there is a diagnosis, overall the group perceived that care available at specialist centres was better than in general hospital settings. Accessing care in specialist centres was challenging due to distance but could be mitigated by remote appointments. Emergency services were perceived to lack understanding of rare diseases, and one participant shared that she carries a letter which explains her disease to non-specialist healthcare professionals. There was a view that care for rare diseases was better on the European mainland than in the UK.

The views expressed by our PPI group were broadly in alignment with the findings of our review, and add important contextual detail to the data. The possibility of attending appointments remotely is an interesting alternative to in-person appointments which may partly address inequities around accessing services which require travelling long distances. The possibility of a diagnosis almost by accident, either due to further tests following an initial incorrect diagnosis, or in an emergency situation, draws out the uncertain and anxious environment in which people with a rare disease live prior to diagnosis. The experience of dismissive attitudes by clinicians was reported by the sole female member of the group, and is similar to that experienced by women with a rare disease in our review.

Implications for research and practice

Research

This review has identified inequities experienced by the rare disease community which require further investigation. Specifically, more comparative research is needed on the experiences of the rare disease community compared with the general population, and within the rare disease community, with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and access to services. Furthermore, future research needs to explicitly seek to identify inequities relating to these experiences. Whilst we identified many studies which reported the experiences of people with a rare disease, these studies were not explicitly aiming to identify issues relating to inequity, and so the experiences we identified were reported almost incidentally amongst wider discussion of the experiences of living or caring for someone with a rare disease. Future research which seeks to identify inequities should draw on frameworks such as PROGRESS+ using a comparative approach.⁸ Our review has also highlighted other areas which may lead to inequity which future research should also focus on.⁸

There is also a particular need for more research on inequities relating to accessing social care services and end of life care, which were relatively underrepresented in the data. We also identified relatively few studies on the prevalence of ethnic minority data in genetic data sets, which we have been alerted to by topic experts as a major concern for equity relating to receipt of a diagnosis (personal correspondence). We are aware of some studies in this area using genetic datasets in the USA, and there may be a need for more research in this area in the UK.^{166, 167} A recent report by the UK NHS Race and Health Observatory does consider ethnic inequities in genomics, but the disease focus is broader than our review, including cancer, inherited and common conditions, in addition to rare conditions.¹⁶⁸ We did not identify data in the report which could be used to inform the present review.

Research which uses hospital records data to identify who and how frequently people within the rare disease community access services may provide additional insight into inequities. A small minority of studies in this review took this approach.

Practice

The evidence gathered in this review suggests that rare diseases should continue to be considered for inclusion in the Core20PLUS5 framework to increase action to reduce health inequalities. We are aware of work underway which is addressing some of the identified inequities, which future work can build on, including:

Lack of knowledge amongst clinicians can be addressed by education and readily accessible information sources for clinicians on rare diseases. This is being developed by the National Genomics Education Programme, including the GeNotes tool which provides clinicians with information on rare genetic diseases,¹⁶⁹ and the Rare Disease Education Hub, which is developing targeted educational interventions for clinicians, including for both genomic and non-genomic forms of rare disease.¹⁷⁰

Lack of information for patients can be addressed through partnerships between patient groups and clinicians to develop relevant and accessible information sources. This is ongoing through organisations such as Unique (<https://rarechromo.org/>), who develop patient information for rare chromosome and genetic disorders which is peer-reviewed by clinicians. There is the potential to extend this work, and further recognition by NHS clinicians of the value of information for patients which is developed by patients.

Lack of care co-ordination can be addressed through the rare disease collaborative networks (RDCNs). RDCNs consist of groups of providers with a shared interest in developing understanding of a particular rare disease or set of rare diseases, and work together to further research, increase knowledge and improve the patient experience for people with rare diseases.⁷ There are currently 20 RDCNs.⁷ Clinical networks such as these will be embedded in NHS service specifications, and underpinned by commissioned research on how best to operationalise better co-ordination of care in the NHS.

Mental health service access is starting to be addressed through the requirement for new and revised NHS service specifications to consider the psychosocial needs of patients, including for people with a rare disease. Furthermore, the aforementioned GeNotes tool will soon include education resources on mental health and psychological services to support those living with rare conditions, their families, and carers. A GeNotes psychiatry working group is currently developing content for this resource.⁷

Age-related concerns relating to transition from paediatric to adult care are being addressed by the Children and Young People's Transformation Programme, which is developing a framework to aid the design of transition pathways that improve health outcomes.⁷

Service access for people with undiagnosed conditions is starting to be addressed through a pilot test of two SWAN (Syndrome Without A Name) clinics in England, one for children and one for adults, drawing on experience of SWAN clinics in Wales.⁷ It is hoped that these pilots will demonstrate how care for patients with undiagnosed conditions can be improved and, in some cases, novel approaches may yield diagnosis.

This ongoing work can contribute to addressing the inequities identified in this review, although wider stakeholder engagement and feedback on this report suggests that the scope of this work needs to be expanded overtime to meet the scale of the challenge.

More generally, there are initiatives underway which seek to develop and extend existing genomic sequencing and DNA testing undertaken for newborns with a view to improving the identification and treatment of rare genetic conditions. Most recently this includes the Generation Study, which tests newborns for over 200 rare diseases (<https://www.generationstudy.co.uk/>).

Inequities relating to dismissive attitudes and place of residence/socioeconomic status

The review also highlighted dismissive attitudes towards women and ethnic minorities. These can be addressed at the level of the needs of people with a rare disease, and also potentially through interventions and service improvements which tackle the needs of these groups in health and social care beyond rare diseases.

Additionally, it is important when designing interventions and services to consider how differences in place of residence and socioeconomic status can affect the experience of diagnosis and access to services, and specific challenges faced by people with a disability.

Strengths and limitations

This scoping review used rigorous, systematic methods. The study identification process used search methods which were tailored for identifying studies on rare diseases, including hand searching the Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases, expert solicitation, and searching for grey literature indexed on topically relevant websites. Rigorous methods were applied to the study selection and data-extraction processes, including checking at all stages by two independent reviewers. Preliminary findings were presented to our stakeholders, topic experts and PPI representatives (albeit solely adults, which is a limitation) with lived experiences of rare diseases, as a sense check that our findings captured their experiences and understanding. To the best of our knowledge, compared to existing reviews of inequities amongst the rare disease community which discuss diagnosis and service access, the current review is more extensive in its coverage of different types of rare diseases and the inequities experienced: we identified 40 systematic reviews which explored inequities relating to rare diseases, but none were as extensive in their coverage of rare diseases or types of inequity.

However, there are challenges to identifying and summarising evidence relating to such an extensive variety of rare diseases, and to the identification of inequities within this evidence. Due to the several thousand different rare diseases which were eligible for inclusion, we were unable to search

for all of these by name in the bibliographic databases which were used to search for studies. Instead, we used generic terminology for rare diseases, in addition to generic terminology which describes genetic diseases. (The Ovid MEDLINE search strategy is reproduced in full in Appendix B). This made the search process manageable (although we still retrieved a very high number of records for title and abstract screening), and the search was tested against a pre-identified set of relevant studies which ascertained that our approach did retrieve potentially relevant studies. However, there is a chance that we may have missed studies which do not self-identify as relating to “rare” or “genetic” diseases, but which only specify the name of a rare disease within the title or abstract, or indexing terms.

Similarly, there were challenges with retrieving studies which report inequity data. Evidence shows that equity data is poorly and infrequently reported in primary studies and systematic reviews.¹⁶¹⁻¹⁶⁴ Our approach used a wide range of terminology which related to inequities, including terminology relating to the PROGRESS+ characteristics, and terminology relating more generically to the experience of diagnosis or accessing services.⁸ However, there is a possibility that there are studies reporting inequities which do not use the same language we used, or which do not refer to inequities in the title or abstract, or indexing terms, which were not retrieved by our search. The use of alternatives to text-based search methods including hand searching, expert solicitation, checking reference lists, forward citation searching, and scanning websites, are mitigating factors against missing studies in the bibliographic database searches.

We suspect that, even if studies are missed, they are unlikely to present a radically different picture of the extent and type of inequities experienced by the rare disease community, and would rather confirm and add weight to the existing inequities that we have identified. We do, however, note some potential gaps in our findings with respect to the type of inequities identified:

- First, relatively little data was identified relating to social care services. This was despite searching social care sources.
- Secondly, in a meeting with topic experts, it was drawn to our attention that the extent of rare diseases affecting ethnic minorities may be underestimated due to the underrepresentation of ethnic minorities in genetic data sets. We are led to believe that this may be more extensively researched in the USA, which was excluded from this review (personal correspondence).^{166, 167} We are aware of a scoping review on methods and mechanisms to measure and monitor outcomes of newborn screening being undertaken at the University of Birmingham, which may address this issue (Mike Harris, UK National

Screening Committee, personal correspondence). The protocol was not published at the time of writing.

Conclusion

This review has drawn attention to experiences of the rare disease community with respect to receipt of a diagnosis and access to services which are different to experiences in the general population, and within the rare disease community itself. Some of these experiences are clearly attributable to factors which are unfair, avoidable and systemic, in particular those which are experienced by subgroups within the rare disease community identified with reference to PROGRESS+, and thus may be considered to be experiences of inequity.⁸ Experiences which are shared across the rare disease community, relating to delayed diagnosis, lack of knowledge, information, care co-ordination and access to various services, also appeared to indicate inequity: overall, the general population are unlikely to have similar experiences of diagnosis or service access, as these problems are less likely to be encountered for more common diseases. However, more comparative data would be helpful to establish the extent of inequities between the rare disease community and general population, and within the rare disease community.

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Appendix A: Methods in full

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

We summarise the inclusion and exclusion criteria using the PICO framework below (Population, phenomenon of Interest and Context), in addition to providing criteria for geographic, study design, date and language limits.¹⁷¹

Population

Include

People or carers of people with a rare disease, defined according to European Union legislation as a disease affecting less than 1 in 2000 people.¹⁷² Specific types of disease include:

- Rare diseases listed on the Orphanet website (c. 7000).¹⁷³
 - To ensure we included all relevant diseases, in cases of uncertainty we inspected the Orphanet website to check whether a disease was rare. We also consulted stakeholders where necessary.

Carers including (but not limited to):

- Family carers
- Unpaid carers

Exclude

Rare disease which fall outside of the UK Rare Diseases Landscape report, namely:¹⁷⁴

- Rare cancers
 - However, we did not exclude rare diseases which manifest as non-malignant tumours or which increase the risk of developing cancer.
- Rare infectious diseases.
- Diseases which do not meet the definition of rare disease above, i.e. diseases affecting more than 1 in 2000 people.

Phenomenon of interest

Include

Data on health inequities as described in the PROGRESS Plus framework:⁸

- PROGRESS criteria:
 - Place of residence
 - Race/ethnicity/culture/language

- Occupation
- Gender/Sex
- Religion
- Education
- Socioeconomic status
- Social capital
- Plus criteria
 - Personal characteristics associated with discrimination (e.g. age, disability, including both visible and invisible disabilities)
 - Features of relationships (e.g. smoking parents, excluded from school)
 - Time-dependent relationships (e.g. leaving the hospital, respite care, other instances where a person may be temporarily at a disadvantage)

Researchers have argued that PROGRESS+ criteria by themselves are not sufficient for identifying potential health inequity.¹⁷⁵ Thus, we also included studies which describe inequity which is not explicitly stated in the PROGRESS-Plus criteria, for example:

- Clinician education/awareness of rare disease services
- Lack of information.

Exclude

Inequities related to the cost of treatment, e.g. the relative cost of making medicines for rare diseases available via the NHS compared to medicines for diseases which are not rare.

Context

Include

EITHER:

1. Data on obtaining a diagnosis, e.g.
 - Accuracy of diagnosis
 - Misdiagnosis
 - Clinician understanding of diagnostic criteria
 - Counselling or support received with diagnosis
 - Time to diagnosis

OR:

2. Data on access to health and social care services, or services more broadly (including voluntary and charitable sector) if these are commissioned by ICSs:
 - Health care services include:
 - Primary care services (e.g. general practice, pharmacy services, opticians)
 - Secondary care services (e.g. mental health services)
 - Tertiary care services (e.g. specialised care, including highly specialised services)
 - Social care services include (but are not limited to):
 - Social services
 - Other services if commissioned by ICSs include:
 - Charitable sector
 - Voluntary sector
 - Issues relating to access include (but are not limited to):
 - Regional access to services
 - Timeliness of service access
 - Other barriers to service access, e.g. gender, socioeconomic status, etc.

Exclude

- Voluntary organisations when not commissioned by ICSs
- Charitable organisations when not commissioned by ICSs

Note: We are not including data on inequity arising from services provided by voluntary or charitable organisations which are not commissioned by ICSs because inequities at this level cannot be directly addressed by DHSC.

Study design

Include

Any primary study design and systematic reviews, specifically:

- Systematic reviews can include:
 - Systematic reviews
 - Meta analyses
 - Scoping reviews
 - Rapid reviews
 - Mapping reviews
 - Qualitative evidence syntheses

All systematic reviews except for scoping and mapping reviews must meet the DARE criteria.³²

Exclude

- Narrative reviews
- Systematic reviews which do not meet the DARE criteria.³²

Geographic location

Include

- Data from UK only. We included studies with data from non-UK countries if UK results were disaggregated.
- No country limit was applied for systematic reviews.

Exclude

- Non-UK primary studies.

Date

Include

- Studies published from 2010 to date of search.

Language

Include

- Studies written in English language only.

Search for studies

The search for studies combined bibliographic database searches with various supplementary searches.

Bibliographic database searches

The bibliographic database search strategy included generic search terms for rare diseases, in addition to generic terms for genetic diseases, which are predominantly comprised of rare diseases. Search terms for rare diseases were based on the search terms used in the Rare Disease Research Landscape project, specifically, the rare disease constructs which are available in Annex 3 of the web report.¹⁵⁷ The purpose of including genetic disease terminology alongside rare disease terminology in the search was not to privilege genetic rare diseases, but due to the fact that our background reading suggested that genetic rare diseases are not routinely described as rare in the literature. As such, we used genetic terminology to retrieve studies of rare genetic diseases, e.g. “genetic disease”, “genetic condition”, “genetic disorder”. Other than this, we did not search for specific types of rare diseases owing to the large volume of diseases in scope for this project and the logistical problem of

how to enter the relevant terminology into a bibliographic database. We also ascertained that studies which meet our eligibility criteria typically either used generic rare disease or genetic disease terminology to describe the population of interest in the title and abstract or controlled vocabulary (e.g. MeSH in MEDLINE), in addition to any descriptive terms for specific rare diseases which are used. We tested this on a sample set of studies which met our eligibility criteria, which were identified from scoping searches and from expert solicitation.

Search terms for rare diseases were combined with search terms which describe access to services and search terms for health equity. Search terms which describe access to services were partly derived from a pre-identified test set of studies which discuss service access for rare diseases. These were supplemented with relevant synonyms. Search terms for equity were partly derived from an existing search filter.¹⁷⁶ These were supplemented with search terms which describe equity issues which are apparent in the rare diseases community based on reading the available literature. These included terms such as ‘knowledge’, ‘education’, ‘information’, ‘communication’, ‘literacy’ and ‘unmet need’, which describe how there is limited knowledge and understanding about rare diseases amongst clinicians which impacts on their ability to signpost patients to services, and the need for better information for rare disease patients and carers.²⁴ We also added additional terms such as ‘geography’ and ‘regional’ which reflects how equity issues sometimes relate to lack of access to services based on geographic or regional location.¹⁷⁷

Finally, we will applied two separate filters to identify UK primary studies and systematic reviews. For UK primary studies, we used a validated UK geographic search filter for databases where this is available.¹⁷⁸ We did not use any study type filter for primary studies. For systematic reviews, we combined the search results with an appropriate selection of descriptive terms for systematic reviews, including “systematic review*”, “evidence syntheses” and “scoping review*”.

We searched the following bibliographic databases which cover both health and social care services literature:

- ASSIA (via ProQuest)
- CINAHL (via EBSCO)
- Embase (via Ovid)
- HMIC (via Ovid)
- MEDLINE (via Ovid)
- Social Policy and Practice (via Ovid)

The MEDLINE search is presented in Appendix A.

Supplementary searches

We carried out supplementary search methods. These included checking the reference lists of included studies and conducting forward citation searches of relevant studies which reported PROGRESS+ data. We also searched the websites of relevant organisations, including organisations recommended by our expert advisory group. Websites searched included:

- Beacon <https://www.rarebeacon.org/>
- Breaking Down Barriers <https://breaking-down-barriers.org.uk/>
- Genetic Alliance UK <https://geneticalliance.org.uk/>
- Medics 4 Rare Diseases <https://www.m4rd.org/>
- Rare Disease UK <https://www.raredisease.org.uk/>
- Rare Minds <https://www.rareminds.org>

We also searched Google Search, primarily but not exclusively with a view to identifying grey literature which is not identified in the bibliographic database searches.

We also carried out hand searching of the Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases, which was pre-identified as containing a high number of potentially relevant studies, and received recommendations of potentially relevant studies from topic experts.

Study selection

Title and abstract records identified via bibliographic databases and forward citation searching were exported to EPPI Reviewer Version 6.0 (EPPI Centre Software, Social Science Research Unit, Institute of Education, University of London, London) and de-duplicated. Four reviewers undertook a screening calibration exercise which sought to identify differences of interpretation in how the screening criteria were applied (SB, CMP, JTC, KS). Following this, two reviewers (SB and CMP) independently screened the remaining records using prioritisation screening in EPPI-Reviewer until the number of identified relevant studies was fewer than one in every 1000 records. Disagreements until this point were resolved through discussion with a third reviewer where necessary (either JTC or KS). After this point, the remaining records were screened by one reviewer (either SB or CMP). Full-texts of relevant studies were sought and screened by two independent reviewers (SB and CMP). Disagreements were resolved as per title and abstract screening disagreements.

Studies identified by checking reference lists, web searches and expert solicitation were screened without exporting the title and abstract records to EPPI-Reviewer by using Microsoft Excel to record screening decisions. This is due to limited functionality for exporting records from reference lists and websites.

Charting the data

Key characteristics of UK primary studies and systematic reviews which met our inclusion criteria were extracted into separate data extraction forms. Data on inequity were coded as relevant to receipt of a diagnosis or access to services, and whether they were shared across the rare disease community, or specific to subgroups within the rare disease community identified in the PROGRESS+ framework (see Box 1).⁸ For inequities that were shared across the rare disease community we differentiated between how these inequities were experienced between the rare disease community and general population, and within the rare disease community. We did not seek to differentiate between these two dimensions of inequity for inequities relating to subgroups identified in the PROGRESS+ framework. This is because it was clear that inequities affecting subgroups within the rare disease community could lead to simultaneous inequities *within* the rare disease community (e.g. between ethnic minority people with a rare disease and white British people with a rare disease) and *between* the rare disease community and general population (i.e. between people with a rare disease and people without a rare disease) (see Box 1). In addition, whilst the inequities experienced by subgroups were deductively derived from the data in the studies with reference to the PROGRESS+ framework, most of the inequities shared across the rare disease community were not pre-specified either in an existing framework or in our protocol, and thus were inductively derived from the data in the studies.⁸

Quality appraisal

As this is a scoping review which seeks to identify and summarise evidence rather than assess the quality of evidence we did not undertake quality appraisal.

Patient and public involvement

The protocol for this review was discussed with the standing PPI group at the Exeter PRP Evidence Review Facility, PERSPEX, who helped to shape the focus of the protocol.²² We also convened a PPI group of four people with lived experience of rare diseases listed on the Orphanet website. This group met on 17th July 2024 to discuss preliminary findings of our review, in a meeting chaired by our PPI co-ordinator, Lauren Asare. The specific disease names are not included in the report to avoid identification of the participants, who belong to communities with small numbers of people.

Presentation of findings

Key characteristics of included UK primary studies and systematic reviews

The key characteristics of the identified studies which met our inclusion criteria were tabulated in format and described narratively for UK primary studies and systematic reviews separately.

Equity data

Data on inequities in the identified studies are described narratively. Specifically, we present the data on inequities in two separate sections:

1. Inequities with respect to receipt of a diagnosis;
2. Inequities with respect to access to services.

Within these sections, we first summarise data on experiences of inequity *shared across the rare disease community*, including:

- a) how these inequities are experienced between the rare disease community and the general population, and
- b) how these inequities are experienced within the rare disease community;

Secondly, we summarise data on experiences of inequities *which relate to subgroups within the rare disease community*, with reference to the PROGRESS+ framework.⁸

Content analysis was undertaken to draw out relevant detail in the relevant studies and describe how this relates to inequity. For the PROGRESS+ data, qualitative and quantitative data are summarised separately where both types of data were identified.⁸

Appendix B: Ovid MEDLINE search

1. (rare adj2 (autoimmune or autosomal or blood or bone or cardia* or cardio* or childhood or chromosom* or CNV or condition* or congenital or connective or contag* or "copy number variant" or derma* or develop* or disease* or disorder* or dominant or familial or frequency or gene* or genotype or haplotype or hereditary or immun* or inflammatory or inherited or kidney or liver or mendelian or metabolic or metasta* or monogenic or muscul* or mutat* or neuro* or paediatric or pathogen or pediatric or phenotype or polygenic or recessive or respira* or skeletal or skin or tumo* or uro* or variant* or "x linked" or zoono*)).tw,kw.
2. "highly specialised technolog*".tw,kw.
3. (orphan adj2 (disease* or drug* or medicine* or medicinal)).tw,kw.
4. orphanet.tw,kw.
5. "syndrome* without a name".tw,kw.
6. (("low frequency" or neglected) adj3 (condition* or disease or disorder*)).tw,kw.
7. (ultraorphan or ultrarare).tw,kw.
8. Rare Diseases/
9. Orphan Drug Production/
10. or/1-9
11. ((gene or genes or genetic* or genomic*) adj2 (condition* or disease* or disorder* or medicine or rare)).tw,kw.
12. exp Sequence Analysis, DNA/
13. exp Genetic Diseases, Inborn/
14. or/11-13
15. 10 or 14
16. ((access* or availab* or entry or referral* or pathway* or uptake or utili?ation) adj4 (care or delay* or diagnos* or healthcare or secondary or service* or specialist or support* or time)).tw.
17. (diagnos* adj4 (delay* or error* or incorrect* or missed or time or specialist* or support)).tw.
18. misdiagnos*.tw.
19. ((healthcare or "health care" or "health service*" or information* or specialist*) adj3 (need* or support*)).tw.
20. ((GP* or "general practitioner*" or primary care) adj2 referral*).tw.
21. exp Health Services Accessibility/
22. exp "Delivery of Health Care"/
23. delayed diagnosis/
24. or/16-23
25. 15 and 24
26. ((gene or genes or genetic* or genomic* or "exome sequencing") adj4 (counsel* or diagnos* or service* or test*)).tw,kw.
27. exp Genetic Services/
28. or/26-27
29. (access* or availab* or delay* or distribution or entry or need or needs or referral* or pathway* or receiving or uptake or utili?ation).tw.
30. exp Health Services Accessibility/
31. exp "Delivery of Health Care"/
32. or/29-31

33. 28 and 32
34. 25 or 33
35. (inequalit* or inequit* or equalit* or equit* or disparit* or divers* or discriminat* or disadvantage* or barrier* or obstacle* or utili*ation or unjust* or unfair* or underserved or minorit* or stigma*).tw.
36. (ethnic* or race or racial* or racis*).tw.
37. ((social* or "socio-economic" or socioeconomic or economic or structural or material) adj3 (advantage* or disadvantage* or exclude* or exclusion or include* or inclusion or status or position or gradient* or hierarch* or class* or determinant*).tw.
38. (health adj3 (gap* or gradient* or hierarch*).tw.
39. Vulnerable populations/
40. social stigma/
41. socioeconomic factors/
42. poverty/
43. social class/
44. Healthcare Disparities/
45. Health Status Disparities/
46. Poverty areas/
47. Urban population/
48. (SES or SEP or sociodemographic* or "socio-demographic*" or income or wealth* or literacy or poverty or education or "educational level" or "educational attainment" or "well educated" or "better educated" or unemploy* or "home owner*" or tenure or affluen* or "well off" or "better off" or "worse off").tw.
49. (unmet adj3 need*).tw.
50. (financial adj1 (resources or situation)).tw.
51. (geograph* or regional or postcode or rural).tw.
52. (communication or information or informed or knowledge).tw.
53. Communication/
54. or/35-53
55. exp United Kingdom/
56. (national health service* or nhs*).ti,ab,in.
57. (english not ((published or publication* or translat* or written or language* or speak* or literature or citation*) adj5 english)).ti,ab.
58. (gb or "g.b." or britain* or (british* not "british columbia") or uk or "u.k." or united kingdom* or (england* not "new england") or northern ireland* or northern irish* or scotland* or scottish* or ((wales or "south wales") not "new south wales") or welsh*).ti,ab,jw,in.
59. (bath or "bath's" or ((birmingham not alabama*) or ("birmingham's" not alabama*) or bradford or "bradford's" or brighton or "brighton's" or bristol or "bristol's" or carlisle* or "carlisle's" or (cambridge not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or ("cambridge's" not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or (canterbury not zealand*) or ("canterbury's" not zealand*) or chelmsford or "chelmsford's" or chester or "chester's" or chichester or "chichester's" or coventry or "coventry's" or derby or "derby's" or (durham not (carolina* or nc)) or ("durham's" not (carolina* or nc)) or ely or "ely's" or exeter or "exeter's" or gloucester or "gloucester's" or hereford or "hereford's" or hull or "hull's" or lancaster or "lancaster's" or leeds* or leicester or "leicester's" or (lincoln not nebraska*) or ("lincoln's" not nebraska*) or (liverpool not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ("liverpool's" not (new south wales* or nsw)) or ((london not (ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or ("london's" not (ontario* or

ont or toronto*)) or manchester or "manchester's" or (newcastle not (new south wales* or nsw) or ("newcastle's" not (new south wales* or nsw)) or norwich or "norwich's" or nottingham or "nottingham's" or oxford or "oxford's" or peterborough or "peterborough's" or plymouth or "plymouth's" or portsmouth or "portsmouth's" or preston or "preston's" or ripon or "ripon's" or salford or "salford's" or salisbury or "salisbury's" or sheffield or "sheffield's" or southampton or "southampton's" or st albans or stoke or "stoke's" or sunderland or "sunderland's" or truro or "truro's" or wakefield or "wakefield's" or wells or westminster or "westminster's" or winchester or "winchester's" or wolverhampton or "wolverhampton's" or (worcester not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or ("worcester's" not (massachusetts* or boston* or harvard*)) or (york not ("new york*" or ny or ontario* or ont or toronto*)) or ("york's" not ("new york*" or ny or ontario* or ont or toronto*))))).ti,ab,in.

60. (bangor or "bangor's" or cardiff or "cardiff's" or newport or "newport's" or st asaph or "st asaph's" or st davids or swansea or "swansea's").ti,ab,in.
61. (aberdeen or "aberdeen's" or dundee or "dundee's" or edinburgh or "edinburgh's" or glasgow or "glasgow's" or inverness or (perth not australia*) or ("perth's" not australia*) or stirling or "stirling's").ti,ab,in.
62. (armagh or "armagh's" or belfast or "belfast's" or lisburn or "lisburn's" or londonderry or "londonderry's" or derry or "derry's" or newry or "newry's").ti,ab,in.
63. or/55-62
64. (exp africa/ or exp americas/ or exp antarctic regions/ or exp arctic regions/ or exp asia/ or exp australia/ or exp oceania/) not (exp United Kingdom/ or europe/)
65. 63 not 64
66. 34 and 54 and 65
67. ((systematic or Cochrane or effectiveness or qualitative or mapping or overview or realist or scoping or umbrella) adj2 review*).tw.
68. (metasynthes?s or "meta synthes?s" or "meta ethnography" or "meta analys?s").tw.
69. ((integrative or integrated) adj1 review*).tw.
70. ((evidence or research) adj1 synthes?s).tw.
71. systematic review.pt.
72. meta-analysis.pt.
73. or/67-72
74. 34 and 54 and 73
75. 66 or 74
76. limit 75 to yr="2010 -Current"

Appendix C. Bibliographic database search results

Table A1. Bibliographic database search results

Database	Hits
ASSIA	478
CINAHL	6673
Embase	15631
HMIC	176
MEDLINE	3837
Social Policy and Practice	61
TOTAL	26856
DUPLICATES	4238
TOTAL UNIQUE	22618

Appendix D: PRISMA flow diagram

Figure 13. PRISMA flow diagram

Narrative summary of PRISMA flow diagram

The bibliographic database searches identified 26,856 title and abstract records. Following the removal of duplicates there were 22618 title and abstract records remaining. Of these, 178 were considered relevant at title and abstract screening. Full-texts for all 178 records were successfully retrieved, of which 72 were considered relevant including 47 UK primary studies^{11, 17-20, 33-35, 42-45, 47-51, 53, 56, 57, 60, 61, 63, 66, 71, 72, 74, 76, 78, 80-82, 92, 93, 98, 99, 101-104, 107, 109-112, 114, 115} and 25 systematic reviews.^{117, 121-123, 125, 126, 128, 129, 132-136, 138, 141, 142, 144, 146, 148-150, 152-155} Forward citation searches identified a further 414 title and abstracts. Of these, 59 were considered relevant at title and abstract screening. Full-texts for all 59 records were successfully retrieved, of which 21 were considered relevant including 8 UK primary studies^{12, 38, 39, 41, 67, 87, 94, 97} and 12 systematic reviews.^{118-120, 127, 130, 139, 140, 143, 145, 147, 151, 156} We also identified relevant full-text UK primary studies via checking reference lists (n=4),^{3, 36, 37, 54} checking the lists of included studies in relevant systematic reviews (n=16),^{40, 52, 55, 62, 64, 65, 70, 73, 75, 88-91, 106, 108, 113} following up conference abstracts (n=6),^{14, 86, 100, 124, 131, 137} hand searching (n=4)^{13, 16, 68, 105} and web searching (n=5).^{15, 58, 59, 69, 77} A further three systematic reviews were also identified via following up conference abstracts.^{124, 131, 137} Nine UK primary studies were identified via expert solicitation.^{24, 46, 79, 83-85, 95, 96, 116}

Appendix E: Excluded full-texts with reasons for exclusion

Table A2. List of excluded full-texts with reasons for exclusion

Author (year): Full Reference
Excluded on context
1. Asnani (2016) : Asnani MR, Quimby KR, Bennett NR, Francis DK. Interventions for patients and caregivers to improve knowledge of sickle cell disease and recognition of its related complications. <i>Cochrane Database Syst Rev</i> . 2016 Oct 6;10(10):CD011175
2. Atkins (2024) : Atkins JC, Padgett CR. Living with a Rare Disease: Psychosocial Impacts for Parents and Family Members—a Systematic Review. <i>Journal of Child and Family Studies</i> . 2024 Feb;33(2):617-36.
3. Ballmann (2022) : Ballmann J, Ewers M. Nurse-led education of people with bleeding disorders and their caregivers: A scoping review. <i>Haemophilia</i> . 2022 Nov;28(6):e153-63.
4. Bin Sawad (2022) : Bin Sawad A, Pothukuchy A, Badeaux M, Hodson V, Bubb G, Lindsley K, Uyei J, Diaz GA. Natural history of arginase 1 deficiency and the unmet needs of patients: A systematic review of case reports. <i>JIMD reports</i> . 2022 Jul;63(4):330-40.
5. Eden (2013) : Eden M, Payne K, Combs RM, Hall G, McAllister M, Black GC. Valuing the benefits of genetic testing for retinitis pigmentosa: a pilot application of the contingent valuation method. <i>British Journal of Ophthalmology</i> . 2013 Aug 1;97(8):1051-6.
6. Garcia-Perez (2021) : García-Pérez L, Linertová R, Valcárcel-Nazco C, Posada M, Gorostiza I, Serrano-Aguilar P. Cost-of-illness studies in rare diseases: a scoping review. <i>Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases</i> . 2021 Dec;16:1-1.
7. Giunti (2013) : Giunti P, Greenfield J, Stevenson AJ, Parkinson MH, Hartmann JL, Sandtmann R, Piercy J, O'Hara J, Casas LR, Smith FM. Impact of Friedreich's Ataxia on health-care resource utilization in the United Kingdom and Germany. <i>Orphanet journal of rare diseases</i> . 2013 Dec;8:1-2.
8. Godaert (2018) : Godaert L, Bartholet S, Colas S, Kanagaratnam L, Fanon JL, Dramé M. Acquired hemophilia A in aged people: a systematic review of case reports and case series. <i>In Seminars in Hematology</i> 2018 Oct 1 (Vol. 55, No. 4, pp. 197-201). WB Saunders.
9. Gulledge (2021) : Gulledge A, Miller S, Mueller M. Social support and social isolation in adults with cystic fibrosis: an integrative review. <i>Journal of Psychosomatic Research</i> . 2021 Nov 1;150:110607.
10. Gurasashvili (2023) : Gurasashvili J, Silverio SA, Hill M, Peter M, Stafford-Smith B, Lewis C. The disequilibrium of hope: A grounded theory analysis of parents' experiences of receiving a "no primary finding" result from genome sequencing. <i>Journal of Genetic Counseling</i> . 2023 Nov 6..
11. Landfeldt (2017) : Landfeldt E, Edström J, Lindgren P, Lochmüller H. Patient preferences for treatments of neuromuscular diseases: a systematic literature review. <i>Journal of Neuromuscular Diseases</i> . 2017 Jan 1;4(4):285-92.
12. Hallett (2011) : Hallett L, Foster T, Liu Z, Blieden M, Valentim J. Burden of disease and unmet needs in tuberous sclerosis complex with neurological manifestations: systematic review. <i>Current medical research and opinion</i> . 2011 Aug 1;27(8):1571-83.
13. Pearson (2018) : Pearson EV, Waite J, Oliver C. Differences in the information needs of parents with a child with a genetic syndrome: A cross-syndrome comparison. <i>Journal of Policy and Practice in Intellectual Disabilities</i> . 2018 Jun;15(2):94-100..
14. Bartolomeu Pires S (2024) : Bartolomeu Pires S, Kunkel D, Kipps C, Goodwin N, Portillo MC. Person-centred integrated care for people living with Parkinson's, Huntington's and Multiple Sclerosis: A systematic review. <i>Health Expectations</i> . 2024 Feb;27(1):e13948.
15. Renedo (2020) : Renedo A, Miles S, Marston C. Transitions to adulthood: self-governance and disciplining in the making of patient citizens. <i>Sociology of Health & Illness</i> . 2020 Mar;42(3):481-95.
16. Seefried (2021) : Seefried, L., Smyth, M., Keen, R. and Harvengt, P., 2021. Burden of disease associated with X-linked hypophosphataemia in adults: a systematic literature review. <i>Osteoporosis International</i> , 32, pp.7-22..
17. Seminog (2022) : Seminog O, Hoang U, Goldacre M, James A. National record-linkage study of hospital admissions for schizophrenia in childhood and adolescence in England. <i>European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry</i> . 2022 Dec;31(12):1943-51.

18. <u>Sepehrpour (2017)</u> Sepehrpour S, McDermott AL, Lloyd MS. Microtia and social media: patient versus physician perspective of quality of information. <i>Journal of Craniofacial Surgery</i> . 2017 May 1;28(3):643-5.
19. <u>Sneller (2014)</u> Sneller J, Buchanan H, Parekh S. The impact of amelogenesis imperfecta and support needs of adolescents with AI and their parents: an exploratory study. <i>International Journal of Paediatric Dentistry</i> . 2014 Nov;24(6):409-16.
Excluded on Country
1. <u>Abrams (2020)</u> : Abrams T, Abbott DW, Mistry B. Ableist constructions of time? boys and men with duchenne muscular dystrophy managing the uncertainty of a shorter life. <i>Scandinavian Journal of Disability Research</i> . 2020 Mar 10;22(1):48-57.
2. <u>Alquati (2022)</u> : Alquati S, Ghirotto L, De Panfilis L, Autelitano C, Bertocchi E, Artioli G, Sireci F, Tanzi S, Sacchi S. Negotiating the Beginning of Care: A Grounded Theory Study of Health Services for Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. <i>Brain Sciences</i> . 2022 Nov 26;12(12):1623.
3. <u>Alugo (2017)</u> : Alugo T, Malone H, Sheehan A, Coyne I, Lawlor A, McNicholas F. Development of a 22q11DS psycho-educational programme: exploration of the views, concerns and educational needs of parents caring for children or adolescents with 22q11DS in relation to mental health issues. <i>Child: care, health and development</i> . 2017 Jul;43(4):527-35.
4. <u>Barrecheguren (2020)</u> : Barrecheguren M, O'Hara K, Wilkens M, Boyd J, Kolda E, Lara B, Chorostowska-Wynimko J, Ferrarotti I, Chlumský J, Clarenbach C, Greulich T. Research priorities in α 1-antitrypsin deficiency: results of a patients' and healthcare providers' international survey from the EARCO Clinical Research Collaboration. <i>ERJ Open Research</i> . 2020 Oct 1;6(4).
5. <u>Bedard (2023)</u> : Bedard KE, Griffith AK, Strittman ME, Eaton A. Behavioral services for individuals with Prader–Willi Syndrome: An initial examination of experiences, needs, and wants of caregivers. <i>Behavioral Interventions</i> . 2023 Jul;38(3):739-49.
6. <u>Bertholet-Thomas (2017)</u> : Bertholet-Thomas A, Berthiller J, Tasic V, Kassai B, Otukesh H, Greco M, Ehrich J, de Paula Bernardes R, Deschênes G, Hulton SA, Fischbach M. Worldwide view of nephropathic cystinosis: results from a survey from 30 countries. <i>BMC nephrology</i> . 2017 Dec;18:1-8.
7. <u>Brizzi (2020)</u> : Brizzi KT, Bridges JF, Yersak J, Balas C, Thakur N, Galvin M, Hardiman O, Heatwole C, Ravits J, Simmons Z, Bruijn L. Understanding the needs of people with ALS: a national survey of patients and caregivers. <i>Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis and Frontotemporal Degeneration</i> . 2020 Jul 2;21(5-6):355-63.
8. <u>Caga (2015)</u> : Caga J, Ramsey E, Hogden A, Mioshi E, Kiernan MC. A longer diagnostic interval is a risk for depression in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. <i>Palliative & supportive care</i> . 2015 Aug;13(4):1019-24.
9. <u>Cheung (2021)</u> : Cheung M, Rylands AJ, Williams A, Bailey K, Bubbear J. Patient-reported complications, symptoms, and experiences of living with X-linked hypophosphatemia across the life-course. <i>Journal of the Endocrine Society</i> . 2021 Aug 1;5(8):bvab070.
10. <u>Christiansen (2016)</u> : Christiansen SC, Davis DK, Castaldo AJ, Zuraw BL. Pediatric hereditary angioedema: onset, diagnostic delay, and disease severity. <i>Clinical pediatrics</i> . 2016 Sep;55(10):935-42.
11. <u>Chrysochoou (2017)</u> : Chrysochoou EA, Hatzigiorgou E, Kirvassilis F, Tsanakas J. Telephone monitoring and home visits significantly improved the quality of life, treatment adherence and lung function in children with cystic fibrosis. <i>Acta Paediatrica</i> . 2017 Nov;106(11):1882-.
12. <u>Denton (2021)</u> : Denton CP, Laird B, Moros L, Luna Flores JL. Things left unsaid: important topics that are not discussed between patients with systemic sclerosis, their carers and their healthcare professionals— a discourse analysis. <i>Clinical Rheumatology</i> . 2021 Apr;40:1399-407.
13. <u>Dzemaili (2017)</u> : Dzemaili S, Tiemensma J, Quinton R, Pitteloud N, Morin D, Dwyer AA. Beyond hormone replacement: quality of life in women with congenital hypogonadotropic hypogonadism. <i>Endocrine connections</i> . 2017 Aug 1;6(6):404-12.
14. <u>Galvin (2017)</u> : Galvin M, Ryan P, Maguire S, Heverin M, Madden C, Vajda A, Normand C, Hardiman O. The path to specialist multidisciplinary care in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis: a population-based study of consultations, interventions and costs. <i>PLoS One</i> . 2017 Jun 22;12(6):e0179796.
15. <u>García-Bravo (2022)</u> : García-Bravo C, Palacios-Ceña D, García-Bravo S, Pérez-Corrales J, Pérez-de-Heredia-Torres M, Martínez-Piédrola RM. Social and family challenges of having a child diagnosed with phelan-McDermid syndrome: a qualitative study of parents' experiences. <i>International journal of environmental research and public health</i> . 2022 Aug 24;19(17):10524...
16. <u>García-Bravo (2023)</u> : García-Bravo, C., Martínez-Piédrola, R.M., García-Bravo, S., Huertas-Hoyas, E., Pérez-De-Heredia-Torres, M. and Palacios-Ceña, D., 2023. Experiences surrounding the diagnostic

process and care among parents of children diagnosed with Phelan–McDermid syndrome: A qualitative study. <i>Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology</i> , 65(7), pp.908-916.
17. <u>Gilmore (2018)</u> : Gilmore L. Supporting families of children with rare and unique chromosome disorders. <i>Research and Practice in Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities</i> . 2018 Jan 2;5(1):8-16.
18. <u>Hailey (2019)</u> : Hailey CE, Tan JW, Dellon EP, Park EM. Pursuing parenthood with cystic fibrosis: reproductive health and parenting concerns in individuals with cystic fibrosis. <i>Pediatric pulmonology</i> . 2019 Aug;54(8):1225-33.
19. <u>Hoegy (2022)</u> : Hoegy D, Guilloux R, Bleyzac N, Gauthier-Vasserot A, Cannas G, Bertrand Y, Dussart C, Janoly-Dumenil A. Pediatric-Adult Care Transition: Perceptions of Adolescent and Young Adult Patients with Sickle Cell Disease and Their Healthcare Providers. <i>Patient preference and adherence</i> . 2022 Jan 1;2727-37.
20. <u>Hogden (2013)</u> : Hogden A, Greenfield D, Nugus P, Kiernan MC. What are the roles of carers in decision-making for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis multidisciplinary care?. <i>Patient preference and adherence</i> . 2013 Feb 28;171-81.
21. <u>Johnson (2016)</u> : Johnson J, Adams-Spink G, Arndt T, Wijeratne D, Heyhoe J, Taylor P. Providing family-centred care for rare diseases in maternity services: Parent satisfaction and preferences when dysmelia is identified. <i>Women and Birth</i> . 2016 Dec 1;29(6):e99-104.
22. <u>Karas (2014)</u> : Karas DJ, Costain G, Chow EW, Bassett AS. Perceived burden and neuropsychiatric morbidities in adults with 22q11.2 deletion syndrome. <i>Journal of Intellectual Disability Research</i> . 2014 Feb;58(2):198-210.
23. <u>Kerstens (2020)</u> : Kerstens HC, Satink T, Nijkrake MJ, De Swart BJ, Van Lith BJ, Geurts AC, Nijhuis-van der Sanden MW. Stumbling, struggling, and shame due to spasticity: a qualitative study of adult persons with hereditary spastic paraplegia. <i>Disability and rehabilitation</i> . 2020 Dec 17;42(26):3744-51.
24. <u>Kline (2023)</u> : Kline E, Garrett AL, Brownstein C, Ziniel S, Payton E, Goldin A, Hoffman K, Chandler J, Weber S. Using social media listening to understand barriers to genomic medicine for those living with Ehlers–Danlos syndromes and hypermobility spectrum disorders. <i>Health Expectations</i> . 2023 Aug;26(4):1524-35.
25. <u>Landau (2022)</u> : Landau EC, Verkleij M, Graziano S, Quittner AL, Georgiopoulos AM, Smith BA, Schechter MS, Abbott J. Mental health screening in Cystic Fibrosis as an intervention: Patient and caregiver feedback on improving these processes. <i>Respiratory Medicine</i> . 2022 Oct 1;202:106955.
26. <u>Lean (2023)</u> : Yao LF, Ferawati K, Liew K, Wakamiya S, Aramaki E. Disruptions in the Cystic Fibrosis Community’s Experiences and Concerns During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Topic Modeling and Time Series Analysis of Reddit Comments. <i>Journal of Medical Internet Research</i> . 2023 Apr 20;25:e45249.
27. <u>Lindsay (2017)</u> : Lindsay S, McAdam L, Mahendiran T. Enablers and barriers of men with Duchenne muscular dystrophy transitioning from an adult clinic within a pediatric hospital. <i>Disability and health journal</i> . 2017 Jan 1;10(1):73-9.
28. <u>Lupu (2023)</u> : Lupu M, Ioghen M, Perjoc RŞ, Scarlat AM, Vladăncenco OA, Roza E, Epure DA, Teleanu RI, Severin EM. The importance of implementing a transition strategy for patients with muscular dystrophy: from child to adult—insights from a tertiary centre for rare neurological diseases. <i>Children</i> . 2023 May 28;10(6):959.
29. <u>Matthie (2016)</u> : Matthie N, Hamilton J, Wells D, Jenerette C. Perceptions of young adults with sickle cell disease concerning their disease experience. <i>Journal of Advanced Nursing</i> . 2016 Jun;72(6):1441-51.
30. <u>Mayo-Gamble (2021)</u> : Mayo-Gamble TL, Quasie-Woode D, Cunningham-Erves J, Rollins M, Schlundt D, Bonnet K, Murry VM. Preferences for using a mobile app in sickle cell disease self-management: descriptive qualitative study. <i>JMIR Formative Research</i> . 2021 Nov 30;5(11):e28678.
31. <u>Sheperd (2010)</u> : Shepherd M. Monogenic diabetes: information seeking and genetic testing access via e-mail. <i>European Diabetes Nursing</i> . 2010 Aug 1;7(2):50-3.
32. <u>Nag (2019)</u> : Nag HE, Hoxmark LB, Nærland T. Parental experiences with behavioural problems in Smith–Magenis syndrome: the need for syndrome-specific competence. <i>Journal of Intellectual Disabilities</i> . 2019 Sep;23(3):359-72.
33. <u>Noone (2019)</u> : Noone D, Skouw-Rasmussen N, Lavin M, van Galen KP, Kadir RA. Barriers and challenges faced by women with congenital bleeding disorders in Europe: results of a patient survey conducted by the European Haemophilia Consortium. <i>Haemophilia</i> . 2019 May;25(3):468-74.
34. <u>O’Mahony (2013)</u> : O’Mahony B, Noone D, Giangrande PL, Prihodova L. Haemophilia care in Europe—a survey of 35 countries. <i>Haemophilia</i> . 2013 Jul;19(4):e239-47.
35. <u>Palareti (2015)</u> : Palareti L, Potì S, Cassis F, Emiliani F, Martino D, Iorio A. Shared topics on the experience of people with haemophilia living in the UK and the USA and the influence of individual and contextual

variables: Results from the HERO qualitative study. International journal of qualitative studies on health and well-being. 2015 Jan 1;10(1):28915.
36. <u>Parker (2022)</u> : Parker M, Hannah M, Zia A. "If I wasn't a girl": Experiences of adolescent girls with heavy menstrual bleeding and inherited bleeding disorders. Research and Practice in Thrombosis and Haemostasis. 2022 Apr 1;6(4):e12727.
37. <u>Rakovec (2023)</u> Rakovec M, Zhu W, Khalafallah AM, Salvatori R, Hamrahian AH, Gallia GL, Ishii M, London Jr NR, Ramanathan Jr M, Rowan NR, Mukherjee D. Patient reported outcomes and treatment satisfaction in patients with cushing syndrome. Endocrine. 2023 Jan;79(1):161-70.
38. <u>Remm (2019)</u> : Remm S, Halcomb E, Stephens M. Experiences of being diagnosed with motor neuron disease: "I just want to know". Collegian. 2019 Oct 1;26(5):550-5.
39. <u>Respondek (2023)</u> Respondek G, Breslow D, Amirghiasvand C, Ghosh B, Bergmans B, van Wyk L, Irfan T, Dossin R, Vanderavero C. The lived experiences of people with progressive supranuclear palsy and their caregivers. Neurology and Therapy. 2023 Feb;12(1):229-47.
40. <u>Rothing (2015)</u> : Røthing M, Malterud K, Frich JC. Family caregivers' views on coordination of care in Huntington's disease: a qualitative study. Scandinavian journal of caring sciences. 2015 Dec;29(4):803-9.
41. <u>Rudebeck (2020)</u> Rudebeck M, Scott C, Sireau N, Ranganath L. A patient survey on the impact of alkaptonuria symptoms as perceived by the patients and their experiences of receiving diagnosis and care. JIMD reports. 2020 May;53(1):71-9.
42. <u>Senger (2016)</u> Senger BA, Ward LD, Barbosa-Leiker C, Bindler RC. Stress and coping of parents caring for a child with mitochondrial disease. Applied Nursing Research. 2016 Feb 1;29:195-201.
43. <u>Stanarevic (2019)</u> Stanarević Katavić S. Health information behaviour of rare disease patients: seeking, finding and sharing health information. Health Information & Libraries Journal. 2019 Dec;36(4):341-56.
44. <u>Teare (2022)</u> Teare H, Argente J, Dattani M, Leger J, Maghnie M, Sherlock M, Ali GC, Francombe J, Marjanovic S. Challenges and improvement needs in the care of patients with central diabetes insipidus. Orphanet journal of rare diseases. 2022 Feb 16;17(1):58.
45. <u>Tung (2022)</u> : Tung JY, Ho JL, Wong R, Fung SC. Dental phenotype in an adolescent with osteogenesis imperfecta type XII. BMJ Case Reports CP. 2022 Apr 1;15(4):e246554.
46. <u>Van Galen (2020)</u> van Galen KP, Lavin M, Skouw-Rasmussen N, Ivanova E, Mauser-Bunschoten E, Punt M, Romana G, Elfvinge P, d'Oiron R, Abdul-Kadir R. Clinical management of woman with bleeding disorders: a survey among European haemophilia treatment centres. Haemophilia. 2020 Jul;26(4):657-62.
47. <u>Van Remmerden (2020)</u> : Van Remmerden MC, Hoogland L, Mous SE, Dierckx B, Coesmans M, Moll HA, Lubbers K, Lincken CR, Van Eeghen AM. Growing up with fragile X syndrome: concerns and care needs of young adult patients and their parents. Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders. 2020 Jun;50:2174-87.
48. <u>Walsh (2023)</u> Walsh C, Leavey G, McLaughlin M. Information provision to caregivers of children with rare dermatological disorders: an international multimethod qualitative study. BMJ open. 2023 Jul 1;13(7):e070840.
49. <u>Ye (2021)</u> Ye Z, Hu W, Wu B, Zhang Y, Lei C, Williams I, Shouval DS, Kanegane H, Kim KM, de Ridder L, Shah N. Predictive prenatal diagnosis for infantile-onset inflammatory bowel disease because of interleukin-10 signalling defects. Journal of pediatric gastroenterology and nutrition. 2021 Feb 1;72(2):276-81.
Excluded on Date
1. <u>Alzheimer's Society (1995)</u> Alzheimer's Disease Society. Services for Younger People with Dementia: A Report by the Alzheimer's Disease Society. Alzheimer's Disease Society. 1995. London
Excluded as duplicate
1. <u>Foley, Geraldine & Timonen, Virpi & Hardiman, Orla. (2012).</u> Patients' Perceptions of Services and Preferences for Care in Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis: A Review. Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. 13. 11-24. 10.3109/17482968.2011.607500.
2. <u>Rapoport (2023)</u> Rapoport M, Bober MB, Raggio C, Wekre LL, Rauch F, Westerheim I, Hart T, van Welzenis T, Mistry A, Clancy J, Booth L. The patient clinical journey and socioeconomic impact of osteogenesis imperfecta: a systematic scoping review. Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases. 2023 Feb 22;18(1):34.
Excluded on Phenomenon of Interest
1. <u>Below (2023)</u> Below N, Morrison D, McGowan R, Jones GC. Diagnostic pitfalls in a young adult with new diabetes. Endocrinology, Diabetes & Metabolism Case Reports. 2023 Oct 1;2023(4).

2.	Burchill (2023) : Burchill E, Rawji V, Styles K, Rooney S, Stone P, Astin R, Sharma N. When months matter; modelling the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the diagnostic pathway of Motor Neurone Disease (MND). <i>Plos one</i> . 2023 Jan 27;18(1):e0259487.
3.	Collaco (2021) Collaço N, Legg J, Day M, Culliford D, Campion A, West C, Darlington AS. COVID-19: impact, experiences, and support needs of children and young adults with cystic fibrosis and parents. <i>Pediatric pulmonology</i> . 2021 Sep;56(9):2845-53.
4.	Cox (2012) Cox NS, Alison JA, Rasekaba T, Holland AE. Telehealth in cystic fibrosis: a systematic review. <i>Journal of telemedicine and telecare</i> . 2012 Mar;18(2):72-8.
5.	Daker-White (2013a) Daker-White G, Greenfield J, Ealing J. "Six sessions is a drop in the ocean": an exploratory study of neurological physiotherapy in idiopathic and inherited ataxias. <i>Physiotherapy</i> . 2013 Dec 1;99(4):335-40.
6.	Davies (2020) Davies G, Rowbotham NJ, Smith S, Elliot ZC, Gathercole K, Rayner O, Leighton PA, Herbert S, Duff AJ, Chandran S, Daniels T. Characterising burden of treatment in cystic fibrosis to identify priority areas for clinical trials. <i>Journal of Cystic Fibrosis</i> . 2020 May 1;19(3):499-502.
7.	Dimitriadis (2012) Dimitriadis PA, Makar RR, Randall JK, Ramus J. Appendiceal torsion associated with undescended caecum: a case report and review of the literature. <i>Case Reports</i> . 2012 Sep 25;2012: bcr2012006932.
8.	Doughty (2018) Doughty, J., Alsayer, F. Special Care Dentistry for patients with rare carbohydrate and protein metabolism disorders: a case series. <i>Journal of Disability & Oral Health</i> . 2018 Feb 21, 19 (1).
9.	Fletcher (2022) Fletcher S, Jenner K, Holland M, Khair K. The lived experience of a novel disruptive therapy in a group of men and boys with haemophilia A with inhibitors: Emi & Me. <i>Health Expectations</i> . 2022 Feb;25(1):443-54.
10.	Fraser (2012) Fraser LK, Childs AM, Miller M, Aldridge J, Manning S, McKinney PA, Parslow RC. A cohort study of children and young people with progressive neuromuscular disorders: clinical and demographic profiles and changing patterns of referral for palliative care. <i>Palliative medicine</i> . 2012 Oct;26(7):924-9.
11.	Gillespie (2021) : Gillespie J, Przybylak-Brouillard A, Watt CL. The palliative care information needs of patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and their informal caregivers: a scoping review. <i>Journal of Pain and Symptom Management</i> . 2021 Oct 1;62(4):848-62.
12.	Gowda (2022) Gowda VL, Fernandez M, Prasad M, Childs AM, Hughes I, Tirupathi S, De Goede CG, O'Rourke D, Parasuraman D, Willis T, Saberian S. Prediagnosis pathway benchmarking audit in patients with Duchenne muscular dystrophy. <i>Archives of disease in childhood</i> . 2022 Feb 1;107(2):160-5.
13.	Hobson (2019) Hobson EV, Baird WO, Bradburn M, Cooper C, Mawson S, Quinn A, Shaw PJ, Walsh T, McDermott CJ. Using telehealth in motor neuron disease to increase access to specialist multidisciplinary care: a UK-based pilot and feasibility study. <i>BMJ open</i> . 2019 Oct 1;9(10):e028525.
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Appendix F: Key characteristics tables of included UK primary studies and systematic reviews

Table A3. Key characteristics of UK primary studies

Study	Disease(s) of interest	Type of study	Participant population, n	PWRD age group (Adult/Child/Both)	Average age (median, range)*	Gender, n (%)*
Akanuwe 2020 ³³	Guillain-Barre Syndrome	Qualitative	PWRD (16)	Adult	NR (range 30-79 years)	Female: 7 (43.75); Male: 9 (56.25)
Al-Attar 2018 ³⁴	Tumour Necrosis Factor Receptor Associated Periodic Syndrome (TRAPS)	Qualitative (Case study)	PWRD (2)	Adult	NR	Female: 2 (100)
Aldiss 2021 ³⁵	Undiagnosed genetic condition	Qualitative	Carers (14)	Child	PWRD: NR (range 14 months-8 years)	Female: 14 (100)
					Carers: NR	
Aljuburi 2012a ³⁷	Sickle cell disease	Qualitative	PWRD (10)	Both	NR (range 9-56)	Female: 8 (80); Male: 2 (20)
Aljuburi 2012b ³⁶	Sickle cell disease	Quantitative	PWRD (40)	NR	NR	Female: 20 (50); Male: 20 (50)
Aubeeluck 2012 ³⁸	Huntington disease	Qualitative	Carers (47)	NR	NR	NR
Bell 2021 ³⁹	Ehlers-Danlos syndrome and hypermobility disorders	Mixed methods	Carers (297, survey; 13, interviews)	Child	NR	<i>Survey</i> Female: 290 (97.64); Male: 7 (2.36)
						<i>Interviews</i> Female: 11 (84.62); Male: 2 (15.38)

Bennett 2021 ⁴⁰	Ehlers–Danlos syndrome	Qualitative	PWRD (17)	Adult	NR	Female: 14 (82.35); Male 3: (17.65)
Berghs 2022 ¹⁸	Sickle cell disease	Mixed methods	PWRD: (37, survey; 8, interviews)	Both	NR	Survey Female: 39 (76.47); Male: 11 (21.57); Other:1 (1.96)
			Carers: (14, survey)			Interviews Female: 6 (75); Male: 2 (25)
Berghs 2024 ⁴¹	Sickle cell disease (during COVID-19 pandemic)	Qualitative	PWRD (8)	Adult	NR	Female: 6 (75); Male: 2 (25)
Booth 2023 ⁴²	Inherited bleeding disorders	Quantitative	PWRD (70)	Adult	39.9 years (mean) (SD 14.74, range 20-80)	Female: 8 (11.43); Male: 62 (88.57)
Cambridge 2016 ⁴³	Cystic fibrosis	Qualitative	PWRD (11)	Adult	NR (range 22-41)	Female: 11 (100)
Cassidy 2023 ⁴⁴	Phenylketonuria	Mixed methods [†]	Carers (169)	Child	NR	Female: 154 (91.67); Male: 14 (8.33) ^a
Chakravorty 2018 ⁴⁵	Sickle cell disease	Quantitative	PWRD (502); Carers (220)	Both	NR	NR
Chudleigh 2016 ¹¹	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative	Carers (22)	Child	PWRD: 5.67 months (mean) (range 3-11 months)	NR
					Carers: NR	
Church Smith n.d. ⁴⁶	Fabry diseases	Quantitative	PWRD (539)	NR	NR	NR

Clark 2019 ¹⁹	Osteogenesis imperfecta	Quantitative	PWRD (92)	Child	9 years (mean) (range 8 months-18 years)	Female: 40 (43); Male: 52 (57)
Cohen 2017 ⁴⁷	22q11 deletion syndrome	Mixed methods [†]	PWRD (1); carers (33)	Child	NR	NR
Collins 2023 ⁴⁸	Cystic fibrosis diabetes	Qualitative	PWRD (8)	Adult	32.88 years (mean)	Female: 4 (50); Male: 4 (50)
Combs 2013 ⁴⁹	Retinal dystrophies	Qualitative	PWRD and carers (20)	Both	NR	NR
Costa 2022 ⁵⁰	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative	<i>Interview</i> Carers (10) ^{‡§}	Both	NR	<i>Interviews</i> Female: 7 (70); Male: 3 (30)
			<i>Feedback events</i> PWRD (1); carers (6) ^{‡§}			<i>Feedback events</i> Female: 4 (66.67); Male: 2 (33.33) (carers only reported)
			<i>Joint event</i> PWRD (1); carers (5) ^{‡§}			<i>Joint event</i> Female: 3 (60); Male: 2 (40) (carers only reported)
			<i>Co-design meetings</i> PWRD (1); carers (1) ^{‡§}			<i>Co-design meetings</i> Female: 1 (100) (carers only reported)
Crowe 2019 ⁵¹	Rare diseases (multiple)	Mixed methods [†]	PWRD (75); carers (89) [‡]	Both	NR	PWRD and carers: Female (71); Male (29)

Cunniff 2015 ⁵²	Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy	Qualitative	Carers: (15, interviews; 55 written accounts of interview questions)	Both	PWRD: 16.1 (mean) (range 8-32)	<i>Interviews</i> Male: 15 (100)
					Carers: 48.4 (mean) (range 34-60)	<i>Written accounts</i> Male: 55 (100)
Daker-White 2015 ⁵⁴	Progressive ataxia	Qualitative	PWRD (38)	Adult	50.5 (range 22-77)	Female: 18 (47.37); Male: 20 (52.63)
Daker-White 2013 ⁵³	Ataxia	Qualitative	PWRD (38) ‡	Adult	50.5 (range 22-77)	Female: 18 (47.37); Male: 20 (52.63)
Dures 2011 ⁵⁵	Epidermolysis Bullosa	Qualitative	PWRD (24)	Adult	NR (range 21-89)	Female: 18 (58.33); Male: 10 (41.67)
Fixter 2017 ⁵⁶	Cystic fibrosis	Qualitative	Carers (12)	Child	PWRD: 8.1 (mean) (SD=4.1, range 2-14)	Female: 10 (83.33); male: 2 (16.67)
					Carers: 45.2 (mean) (SD=9.8, range 35-70)	
Flaherty 2024 ⁵⁷	Trimethylaminuria	Quantitative	PWRD and carers (44)	Both	NR	Female: 34 (77.27); Male: 9 (20.45); Prefer not to say:1 (2.27)
Franklish 2022 ⁵⁸	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative	PWRD and carers (NR)	Both	NR	NR

Genetic Alliance 2023 ⁵⁹	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative (Case studies)	PWRD (6); Carers (3) [‡]	Both	NR	PWRD Female: 3 (50); Male: 3 (50)
						Carers Female: 2 (66.67); Male: 1 (33.33)
Gillfillan 2024 ⁶⁰	Mayer-Rokitansky-Kuster-Hauser syndrome	Qualitative	PWRD (13)	Adult	38.54 (mean) (range 18-59)	Female: 13 (100)
Gleeson 2013 ⁶¹	Congenital adrenal hyperplasia	Quantitative	PWRD (53)	Both (transition from child to adult care)	25.5 (range 18.4-47.8)	Female: 30 (56.60); Male: 23 (43.40)
Griffith 2011 ⁶²	Rare Genetic Intellectual Disability Syndrome (multiple)	Qualitative	Carers (8)	Adult	PWRD: 27 (range 24-44)	PWRD Female: 6 (66.67); Male: 3 (33.33)
					Carers: 54.5 (range 51-72)	Carers Female: 8 (100)
Grose 2014 ⁶³	Hereditary spastic paraparesis	Qualitative	PWRD (14); Carers (6) [‡]	Adult	NR	NR
Gysels 2011 ⁶⁴	Motor neurone disease	Qualitative	PWRD (10) ^b	Adult	42 (median) (range 24-77)	Female: 1 (10); Male: 9 (90)
Hagena 2014 ⁶⁵	Motor Neurone Disease	Mixed methods	Focus groups PWRD (5); carers (8);	NR	PWRD: 67.64 (mean) (range 46-84)	PWRD Female: 9 (81.82); Male: 2 (18.18)
			Interviews PWRD (6); carers (4)		Carers: NR	Carers Female: 6 (50); Male: 6 (50)
			Questionnaire PWRD (19) [‡]			

Haig-Ferguson 2023 ⁶⁶	Oesophageal atresia and tracheo-oesophageal fistula	Qualitative	PWRD (16); carers (23)	Both (transition from child to adult care)	NR	PWRD Female: 14 (87.50); Male: 2 (12.50)
						Carers Female: 21 (91.30); Male: 2 (8.70)
Harris 2018 ⁶⁷	Motor Neurone Disease	Qualitative	PWRD (4)	Adult	NR	NR
Hassal 2022 ⁶⁸	Lysosomal acid lipase deficiency	Qualitative	Carers (8)	Child	NR (all <10)	Female: 5 (62.50); Male: 3 (37.50)
Hay 2022 ⁶⁹	Tuberous sclerosis complex, Bardet Biedl Syndrome, ANCA-associated Vasculitis	Quantitative	PWRD (40)	Both	NR	NR
Hill 2013 ⁷⁰	Motor neurone disease	Qualitative	PWRD (7); carers (7)	Adult	PWRD: 66.4 (mean) (range 46-79)	PWRD Female: 4 (57.14); Male: 3 (42.86)
					Carers: 63.2 (mean) (range 45-70)	Carers Female: 3 (42.86); Male: 4 (57.14)
Husson 2019 ⁷¹	Desmoid fibromatosis	Qualitative	PWRD: (14, focus groups; 13, interviews)	Adult	39.5 (mean) (SD=13.7, range 23-74)	Female: 15 (55.56); Male: 12 (44.44)
Hytiris 2021 ⁷²	Rare diseases (multiple)	Quantitative	PWRD (13); carers (117)	Child	NR	NR
Iles 2010 ⁷³	Cystic fibrosis	Qualitative	PWRD (32) ^{c‡}	Both	19.1 (mean)	Female: 17 (53.13); Male: 15 (46.88)
Kalsi 2012 ⁷⁴	Inherited bleeding disorders	Quantitative	PWRD (105) [‡]	Both	NR	NR

Khair 2019 ⁷⁶	Inherited bleeding disorders	Mixed methods [†]	Carers (231)	Child	NR	Female: 131 (56.96); Male: 99 (43.04) ^d
Khair 2022 ¹⁷	Inherited bleeding disorders	Mixed methods	PWRD and carers: (280, survey; 11 focus group; 2, interview)	Both	NR	Survey Female: 280 (100)
						Focus groups and interviews Women: 13 (100)
Khair 2013 ⁷⁵	Bleeding disorders	Mixed methods	PWRD: (45, survey; NR, focus group)	Both	Survey: 19.8 (mean) (SD= 5.21, range 9-34)	Survey Female: 45 (100)
						Focus groups Female: (100)
McDonald 2019 ⁷⁸	Tuberous sclerosis complex	Qualitative	PWRD (2); carers (11)	Both	NR	PWRD Female: 1(50), NR: 1 (50)
						Carers Female: 4 (66.67); Male:2 (33.33); NR: 5
McInnes-Dean 2024 ⁷⁹	Genetic diseases (unspecified)	Qualitative	Carers (48) ‡	Child	Carers: 34.5 (mean) (range 28-49)	Carers Female: 42 (88.5); Male: 6 (13%)
McMullan 2022 ⁸⁰	Rare diseases (multiple)	Mixed methods	Carers: (57, survey; 32, workshop)	Both	NR	Survey Female: 48 (84.21); Male: 9 (15.79)
Miles 2019 ⁸¹	Sickle Cell Disease	Qualitative	PWRD (48)	Both	NR (range 13-21)	Female: 30 (62.50); Male: 18 (37.50);

Morgan 2021 ⁸²	Dystonia	Qualitative	PWRD (8)	Adult	52.13 (mean) (range 31-66)	Female: 5 (62.50); Male: 3 (37.50)
Morris 2023 ¹⁶	Ataxia	Quantitative	PWRD (181) [§]	Both	NR	NR
Morris 2022 ¹⁵	Rare diseases (multiple)	Mixed methods	<i>Interviews</i> PWRD (7); carers (8)	Both	NR	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 434 (85.27); Male: 73 (14.34); Other: 2 (0.39) ^e
			<i>Survey</i> PWRD (760); carers (446) [‡]			<i>Carers</i> Female: 235 (87.69); Male: 32 (11.94); Other: 1 (0.37) ^e
MSA Trust 2019a ⁸³	Multiple system atrophy	Quantitative	PWRD and carers (284)	Adult	NR	<i>PWRD and carers</i> : Female: 122 (47%); Male: 138 (53%)
MSA Trust 2019b ⁸⁴	Multiple system atrophy	Quantitative	Carers (371)	Adult	NR	Female (71); Male (28)
MSA Trust 2022 ⁸⁵	Multiple system atrophy	Mixed methods [†]	PWRD (215) ^f ; Carers (305)	Adult	NR	<i>PWRD</i> : Female: 108 (51); Male: 104 (49)
						<i>Carers</i> : Current carers- Female: 127 (60); Male: 83 (40) Former carers- Female: 56 (62); Male: 34 (38)

Neelamekam 2017 ⁸⁶	Lipoprotein lipase deficiency	Mixed methods	PWRD (3); carers (2)	Adult	PWRD: 44.67 (mean) (range 28-64)	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 2 (66.67); Male: 1 (33.33)
					Carers: NR	
O'Brien 2011a ⁹¹	Motor neurone disease/Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	Qualitative	PWRD (24); carers (28)	Adult	NR	NR
O'Brien 2011b ⁸⁸	Motor neurone disease/Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis	Qualitative	PWRD (24); carers (28)	Adult	NR	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 16 (64); Male: 9 (36) ^f
						<i>Carers</i> NR
O'Brien 2012a ⁸⁹	Motor neurone disease/Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	Qualitative	Carers (28)	Adult	NR	<i>Carers</i> Male: 14 (50); Female: 14 (50)
O'Brien 2012b ⁹⁰	Motor neurone disease/Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis	Mixed methods	<i>Quantitative</i> PWRD: (97)	Adult	<i>Quantitative</i> Females: 65.84 (mean) (SD=10.95); Males: 64.24 (mean) (SD=10.35);	<i>Quantitative</i> Females: 48 (49.48); Males: 49 (50.51)
			<i>Qualitative</i> PWRD (24); Carers (18)		<i>Qualitative</i> NR	<i>Qualitative</i> PWRD: Female: 16 (64); male: 9 (36) ^g ; Carers: NR
O'Brien 2015 ⁸⁷	Motor Neurone Disease	Qualitative	Carers (21)	NR	NR	Female: 10 (47.62); Male: 11 (52.38)

O'Brien 2023 ¹²	Motor neurone disease	Mixed methods [†]	PWRD (69); Carers (39)	Adult	PWRD: 61 (mean) (SD=10.22, range 32-89)	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 27 (39.71); Male: 41 (60.29) ^h
					Carers-55 (mean) (SD=12.83, range 29-80)	<i>Carers</i> Female: 28 (77.78); Male: 8 (22.22) ^h
Oerton 2011 ⁹²	Medium chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase deficiency	Quantitative	PWRD (190) ⁱ	Child	9.7 days (mean)	Female: 90 (47.62%); Male: 99 (52.38%); Missing:1
Pak 2020 ⁹³	Acromegaly	Qualitative	PWRD (18)	Adult	52 (mean) (range 30–72)	Female: 11 (61.11); Male: 7 (38.89)
Pavey 2013 ⁹⁴	Motor neurone disease	Qualitative	PWRD (42)	Adult	NR	Male: 31 (73.81); Female: 11 (26.19)
Peter 2022 ⁹⁵	Rare diseases (multiple)	Mixed methods	<i>Quantitative</i> PWRD and Carers (77)	Both	NR	NR
			<i>Qualitative</i> PWRD and Carers (39)			
Peter 2024 ⁹⁶	Genetic diseases	Qualitative	Carers (48) ‡	Child	Carers-34.5 (mean) (range 28-49)	<i>Carers</i> Female: 42 (88%); Male: 6 (13%)
					PWRD:NR	
Pinto 2021 ⁹⁷	Motor neurone disease	Qualitative	PWRD (25); Carers (10)	Adult	NR	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 10 (40); male: 15 (60)

						<i>Carers</i> Female: 5 (50); male: 5 (50)
Limb 2010 (Rare Disease UK) ⁷⁷	Rare diseases (multiple)	Mixed methods	PWRD (268); Carers (279) ‡	NR	NR	NR
Muir 2016 (Rare Disease UK) ³	Rare diseases (multiple: >450)	Mixed methods	PWRD and carers (1203)	Both	NR	NR
Renedo 2019 ⁹⁸	Sickle Cell Disease	Qualitative	PWRD (48)	Both (transition from child to adult care)	16.6 (mean) (range 13-21)	Female: 30 (62.50); male: 18(37.50)
Rodger 2015 ²⁰	Duchenne muscular dystrophy	Quantitative	PWRD and carers (226)§	Both	PWRD: 24.1 (mean)	NR
					Carers: NR	
Shah 2014 ⁹⁹	Rare neurodegenerative conditions	Qualitative	PWRD (15); carers (11)	Adult	PWRD: 51.82 (mean) (range 27-79)	NR
					Carers: NR	
Sharma 2020 ¹⁰⁰	Cystic Fibrosis	Qualitative	PWRD (16)	Adult	48 (mean) (range 24-69)	Female: 10 (62.50); Male :6 (37.50)
Simpson 2018 ¹⁰²	Adrenal Insufficiency/ congenital adrenal hyperplasia	Mixed methods	Carers: (20, qualitative; 57, quantitative)	Child	PWRD: NR (range 3 months-10 years)	<i>Qualitative</i> Female: 14 (70); Male: 6 (30)
					Carers: NR	<i>Quantitative</i> Female: 43 (75); Male: 14 (25)
Simpson 2021 ¹⁰¹	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative	PWRD (7); Carers (8)	Both	NR	NR
Skirton 2010 ¹⁰³	Huntington disease	Quantitative	Carers (108) [§]	Adult	53.66 (mean) (SD=12.66)	Female: 69 (63.89); Male: 39 (36.11)

Skrobanski 2023 ¹⁰⁴	Tuberous sclerosis complex	Mixed-methods [†]	Carers (59)	Both	20.0 (mean) (SD=13.5)	Female: 56 (95)
Song 2024 ¹⁰⁵	Fibrous dysplasia / McCune albright syndrome	Quantitative	PWRD (51)	Adult	51.0 (Interquartile range: 34.5–57.5)	Female: 36 (70.59)
Spencer-Tansley 2018 ¹⁰⁶	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative	PWRD and siblings (>60)	Child	NR	NR
Spencer-Tansley 2022 ¹⁰⁷	Rare diseases (multiple)	Quantitative	PWRD (913); Carers (340)	Both	NR	<i>Carers</i> Female: 315 (92.38) ^j
						<i>PWRD</i> Female: 778 (83.93) ^j
Specialised Healthcare Alliance 2023 ²⁴	Rare diseases (multiple)	Qualitative	Patients (NR); Carers (NR) ‡	NR	NR	NR
Taylor 2014 ¹⁰⁸	Motor neurone disease	Qualitative	PWRD (13); carers (10) ^k	Adult	PWRD: NR (Range 43-82)	PWRD - male 8 (61.54); female: 5 (38.46)
					Carers: NR (Range 32-76 years)	Carers- male: 5 (50); female: 5 (50)
Trimmer 2024 ¹⁰⁹	Duchenne muscular dystrophy	Mixed methods	<i>Focus groups</i> PWRD (8); carers (14)	Child	NR	<i>Focus groups</i> PWRD: Male: 8 (100)
						<i>Focus groups</i> Carers: Female: 13 (92.86); Male: 1 (7.14)

			<i>Survey</i> PWRD (18); carers (16)			<i>Survey</i> NR
Twigg 2021 ¹¹⁰	Polyneuropathy Organomegaly Endocrinopathy Monoclonal gammopathy Skin changes (POEMS) syndrome	Mixed methods (case study)	PWRD (1); Carer (1)	Adult	PWRD (71)	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 1 (100)
						<i>Carer</i> Male:1 (100)
Vallortigara 2023 ¹⁴	Progressive ataxias	Quantitative	PWRD (234); carers (39) [§]	Both	NR	<i>PWRD and carers</i> Female: 142 (52.59); Male: 128 (47.41)
Vasillca 2021 ¹¹¹	IgA Nephropathy	Qualitative	PWRD and carers (498)	NR	NR	NR
Walton 2023 ¹³	Rare diseases	Quantitative	PWRD (760); carers (446) [‡]	Adult	NR	<i>PWRD</i> Female: 434 (85.27); Male: 73 (14.34); Other: 2 (0.39) ^e
						<i>Carers</i> Female: 235 (87.69); Male: 32 (11.94); Other: 1 (0.37) ^e
Whitaker 2021 ¹¹²	Haemophilia A or B	Mixed methods	PWRD: (9, focus groups; 7, interviews; 226, survey)	Adult	Focus groups and interviews: 41 (median) (range 26–62)	<i>Focus groups</i> Female: 16 (100)
						<i>Interviews</i> Female: 7 (100)

					Survey: NR	Survey Female: 226 (100)
Whitehead 2012 ¹¹³	Motor neurone disease	Qualitative	PWRD (24); carers (28)	Adult	NR	Carers Female:14(50); Male:14(50)
						PWRD NR
Wilson 2019 ¹¹⁴	Cystic Fibrosis	Mixed methods	PWRD (21)	Adult	30.9 (mean) (SD=9.1, range 18-55)	Female: 8 (38.10); Male: 13 (61.90)
Wray 2021 ¹¹⁵	Long-segment congenital tracheal stenosis	Mixed methods	Carers (14)	Child	NR	Female: 11 (78.57); Male: 3 (21.43)
Wright 2022 ¹¹⁶	Previously undiagnosed developmental disorders (multiple)	Quantitative	PWRD and carers (13,450) [¶]	Both	PWRD: 7 (median) (range 0-63)	PWRD Female (42); Male (58)
					Carers: 31 (median) (range 15-90 at proband's birth)	

Abbreviations: PWRD= people with a rare disease; NR= not reported

Key: *=For studies where participant population are carers only, average age and gender distribution are sometimes also reported for PLWRD who are cared for;
†=survey studies which include both closed and open-ended questions and therefore classified as mixed methods; ‡=studies include service provider perspectives as well, but these are not reported here; §=studies including non-UK population samples as well, but only characteristics of UK population samples reported here;
¶=includes both UK and Ireland participants.

Footnotes: a= values calculated from 168 rather than 169 (sample total) due to missing data ; b=study included non-rare disease population sample as well, but only characteristics of rare disease population sample reported here; c=50 young people were interviewed, but only 32 young people who experienced transition and/or adult CF services are the focus of this study, and only their characteristics reported; d=values calculated from 230 rather than 231 (sample total) due to missing data; e=gender reported only for survey participants; values calculated from subsample of participant population due to missing data; f= For the PWRD group, some responses were filled in by family members, friends or healthcare professionals on behalf of the PWRD; g=values calculated from 25, rather than 24 (sample total) due to missing

data; h=calculated from 68, rather than 69 (patient sample total) and 36 rather than 39 (carer sample total) due to missing data; i=1.5 million newborns were screened, but only 190 are the focus of this study as they were presumed positive and referred for further diagnostic testing; j=calculated from 341, rather than 340 (carer total sample) and 927 rather than 913 (patient total sample) due to missing data; k=partners have been classified as carers in this study; l=in some cases both parents and offspring were analysed as a single patient unit during genomic analyses, but data reported here is divided into PLWRD (offspring) and carers (parents) for clarity.

Table A4. Key characteristics of included systematic reviews

Study	Disease(s) of interest	Included studies, n	Type of included study (quant/qual/mixed methods)	Countries/regions where studies carried out	Participant population	Patient age group (Adult/child/both)
Anderson 2021 ¹¹⁷	Hypermobile Ehlers–Danlos syndrome*	13	Qualitative; mixed methods	Belgium, Norway, Spain UK, USA	PWRD; carers [†]	Both
Anestis 2020 ¹¹⁸	Rare disease (multiple)	47	All	Australia, Canada, Europe, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, South Africa, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD [†]	Adult
Aoun 2013 ¹¹⁹	Motor neuron disease	59	All	Australia, Canada, Germany, Italy, Japan, Europe, Sweden, UK, USA	Carers	NR
Assalone 2024 ¹²⁰	Rare diseases (multiple)	49	Quantitative; qualitative	Argentina, Australia, Canada, China, Denmark, Germany, Italy, Jordan, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Taiwan, Turkey, UK, USA	Carers	Child
Behan 2017 ¹²¹	Primary ciliary dyskinesia	14	All	Belgium, Denmark, International (25 countries), Italy, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Both
Benenson 2017 ¹²²	Sickle cell disease	14	Quantitative	UK, USA	PWRD	Both
Best 2022 ¹²³	Rare diseases (multiple: non-cancer related)	20	All	Brazil, Canada, Malaysia, Mexico, UK, USA,	PWRD; carers [†]	Both

Boersema-Wijma 2023 ¹²⁴	Huntington's disease	38	Quantitative; qualitative	Australia, Canada, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD; carers ⁺	Both
Brandt 2022 ¹²⁵	Spinal muscular atrophy	24	All	Australia, Canada, China, Europe, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, Taiwan, Turkey, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Both
Bulgin 2018 ¹²⁶	Sickle cell disease	27	All	Brazil, Jamaica, Nigeria, UK, USA,	PWRD	Both
Chrastina 2023 ¹²⁷	Duchenne's Muscular Dystrophy	8	Qualitative	Colombia, Germany, India, Norway, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Both
Coyne 2017 ¹²⁸	Cystic fibrosis	22	Quantitative; qualitative	Australia, Canada, France, Germany, Ireland, UK, USA,	PWRD; carers	Both
Fairweather 2022 ¹²⁹	Cystic fibrosis	17	Qualitative	Brazil, Canada, Ireland, UK, USA	PWRD	Both
Flemming 2020 ¹³⁰	Motor neuron disease *	41	Qualitative	Australia, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Adult
Foley 2012 ¹³²	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis	47	All	Australia, Canada, Italy, Ireland, Japan, Netherlands, New Zealand, Portugal, Scotland, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD	Both
Foley 2018 ¹³¹	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis	47	All	Australia, Canada, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Norway, South Korea, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	NR
Gage 2012 ¹³³	Cystic fibrosis	9	Quantitative; qualitative	Australia, Poland, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD	NR
Kamga 2020 ¹³⁴	Fragile X syndrome	12	Qualitative	Canada, Netherlands, South Africa, USA	Carers	Child
Kayle 2017 ¹³⁵	Sickle cell disease	39	All	UK, USA	PWRD, carers ⁺	Both
Khan 2023 ¹³⁶	Sickle cell disease	59	Quantitative	Brazil, Canada, France, French Guiana, Italy, Jamaica, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Both
Lal 2022 ¹³⁷	Rare diseases (multiple)	33	Quantitative; qualitative	Australia, Canada, Colombia, Denmark, Egypt, Europe, Germany, Greece, Italy,	PWRD	Both

				Netherlands, Norway, Serbia, Taiwan, UK, USA		
Lapite 2023 ¹³⁸	Sickle cell disease	8	Qualitative	Canada, UK, USA,	PWRD; carers	Both
McMullan 2022 ¹³⁹	Rare diseases (multiple)	35	All	Australia, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, UK, USA	Carers	NR
Milo 2022 ¹⁴⁰	Cystic fibrosis	13	Qualitative; mixed methods	Australia, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Both
Nevin 2023 ¹⁴¹	Childhood dementias (multiple)	19	Quantitative; qualitative	Australia, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Japan, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden, UK, USA	Carers	Child
Nunnemann 2012 ¹⁴²	Frontotemporal lobar degeneration	19	All	NR	Carers	NR
Oh 2017 ¹⁴³	Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis/ motor neuron disease	37	All	Australia, Canada, England, Germany, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Scotland, Singapore, Sweden, Turkey, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	NR
Poku 2018 ¹⁴⁴	Sickle cell disease	40	All	Jamaica, Middle East, Sub-Saharan Africa, UK, USA	PWRD	Both
Poppe 2020 ¹⁴⁵	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	48	Quantitative; qualitative	Australia, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Norway, South Korea, Sweden, Turkey, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Both
Porteous 2021 ¹⁴⁶	Duchenne's Muscular Dystrophy	21	Qualitative	NR	Carers	Both
Rance 2019 ¹⁴⁷	Sickle cell disease	6	Quantitative; qualitative	Brazil, Cameroon, Jamaica, USA	PWRD	Adult
Rea 2021 ¹⁴⁸	Sickle cell disease	44	All	NR	PWRD; carers ^{at}	Both
Rodrigues 2016 ¹⁴⁹	Sickle cell disease	16	All	NR	PWRD; carers	Child
Sanigorska 2022 ¹⁵⁰	Bleeding disorders *	28	Quantitative; qualitative	Brazil, Canada, Europe, France Germany, India, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Turkey, UK, USA	PWRD [†]	Both

Somanadhan 2023 ¹⁵¹	Rare diseases (multiple)	8	Qualitative; mixed methods	Australia, Netherlands UK, USA	PWRD	Both
Tschamper 2022 ¹⁵²	Rare epilepsy-related disorders and intellectual disability (multiple)	17	All	Australia, Brazil Canada, France, Ireland, Netherlands, UK, USA	PWRD; carers [†]	Both
Tsitsani 2023 ¹⁵³	Rare diseases (multiple)	25	All	Australia, Canada, China, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, UK, USA	PWRD; carers	Adults
von der Lippe 2017 ¹⁵⁴	Rare diseases (multiple)	21	Qualitative	Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD	Both
von der Lippe 2022 ¹⁵⁵	Rare diseases (multiple)	33	Qualitative	Australia, Canada, China, Denmark, Ireland, Italy, Montenegro, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Taiwan, UK, USA	Carers	Both
Young 2023 ¹⁵⁶	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis	44	All	Australia, Germany, Italy, Japan, Korea, Netherlands, Singapore, Sweden, UK, USA	PWRD; carers [†]	Adults

Abbreviations: PWRD=people with a rare disease; UK=United Kingdom; USA=United States of America

Key: *= includes multiple disease types/variants; †=studies including service provider perspectives as well, but these are not reported here

Footnotes: a=studies including sibling perspectives were also included in this review, but these are not reported here

Appendix G: UK primary studies and systematic reviews with multiple rare diseases

Table A5. Primary studies and systematic reviews reporting multiple rare diseases which are not limited to subtypes or categories of rare disease

Author year	Study type (primary study or SR)	Number of rare diseases	Rare diseases reported
Muir 2016 (Rare Disease UK) ³	Primary study	>450	NR
Morris 2022 ¹⁵	Primary study	221*	NR [‡]
Limb 2010 (Rare Disease UK) ⁷⁷	Primary study	119*	See Annex 1 of Limb 2010 for full list. ⁷⁷
Hytiris 2021 ⁷²	Primary study	103*	See Table 2 of Hytiris 2021 for full list. ⁷²
Tsitsani 2023 ¹⁵³	SR	49 [†]	Achondroplasia; Aicardi syndrome; Angelman syndrome; Arginine succinic aciduria; autoimmune thrombocytopenia; Becker syndrome; Blood diseases; Chromosome 22 Ring; Congenital malformations; Cystic fibrosis; Diseases of skin and subcutaneous tissue; Diseases of the eye and its annexes; Diseases of the genitourinary system; Disorders of the nervous system; Diseases of the respiratory system; Duchenne muscular dystrophy; Fragile X syndrome; Fryns syndrome; Gastrointestinal diseases; Genetic disorders; glycogen storage disease; Goldenhar syndrome; Guillain–Barré syndrome; Haemophilia; Hirschsprung disease; Immune system disorders; infantile agranulocytosis; Langerhans cell histiocytosis; Lesch–Nyhan syndrome; Limb–girdle muscular dystrophies; Locked-in syndrome; Mastocytosis; Moebius syndrome; Mucopolysaccharidosis type III; Musculoskeletal diseases, Metabolic disorders; Metachromatic leukodystrophy; myasthenia gravis; Neurodevelopmental disorders; Patent ductus arteriosus; polysyndactyly; Prader–Willi syndrome; Rare Diseases that require mechanical ventilation; Rett syndrome; spinal muscular dystrophies; tetralogy of Fallo; Wilson’s disease; Wolf–Hirschhorn syndrome
Von der Lippe 2017 ¹⁵⁴	SR	31	Addison’s disease; Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis; Anorectal atresia; Arthrogryposis, multiplex congenital; Bechet’s disease; Cystic fibrosis; Duchenne

			muscular dystrophy; Dysmelia; Epidermolysis bullosa; Fabry disease; Fragile X syndrome; Gaucher's disease; Haemophilia; Horton's disease; Idiopathic pulmonary hypertension; Locked-in syndrome and a sixth syndrome; Marfan syndrome; Mastocytosis; Mixed connective tissue disease; Neurodegeneration with brain iron accumulation; Phelan-McDermid syndrome; Phenylketonuria; Poland syndrome; Pulmonary artery stenosis; Rare congenital medical diagnoses (not specified); Scleroderma; Tuberous sclerosis; Very Rare Syndrome ;Wilson's disease; 22q11 deletion syndrome
Von der Lippe 2022 ¹⁵⁵	SR	29 [†]	Alagille syndrome; Amelogenesis imperfecta; Angelman syndrome; Bartter syndrome; Brdet-Biedl syndrome; Congenital craniofacial anomaly; Cornelia de Lange; Cri du Chat; Epidermolysis bullosa; Haemophilia A and B; Juvenile Huntington's disease; Mucopolysaccharidosis type II/II/III/VI ; Neuroendocrine hyperplasia of infancy; Prader-Willis syndrome; Rett syndrome; Several chromosomal disorders; Sturge-Weber syndrome; Silver-Russel syndrome; Smith-Magenis syndrome; Spinal muscular atrophy I & II; Trisomy 9, 13, 18; Urea cycle disorders; 16p11.2 deletion syndrome
Assalone 2024 ¹²⁰	SR	21 [†]	Achondroplasia, Angelman syndrome; Becker Muscular Dystrophy; Congenital anomalies; Duchenne muscular dystrophy, Dysmelia, Oesophageal atresia; Haemorrhagic disorder, Juvenile idiopathic rheumatoid arthritis; Leukodystrophies; Marfan syndrome; Metabolic disorders; Mitochondrial respiratory chain disorder; Mucopolysaccharidosis type III, Neuromuscular disease; Phenylketonuria; Prader Willi Syndrome; Rare disease; Rett syndrome; Short bowel syndrome, Spinal Muscular Atrophy Type I and II
McMullan 2022 ¹³⁹	SR	19 [†]	ANCA-associated vasculitis; CDKL5 disorder; Dravet syndrome; Duchenne muscular dystrophy; Erdheim-Chester disease; Hereditary angioedema; Huntington's Disease; Mucopolysaccharidosis; Multiple system atrophy; Neuromyelitis Optica; Parents of disabled children; Pompe disease; Progressive Supranuclear Palsy; Rare neurodevelopmental diseases; Rett syndrome; Spinal Muscular Atrophy; Rare disease; Systemic Sclerosis; Von Hippel-Lindau disease;
Walton 2023 ¹³	Primary study	15	Allergic broncho pulmonary aspergillosis; Aplastic anaemia; Ataxia; Behcet's syndrome; Common variable immune deficiency; Dravet syndrome; Ehlers-

			Danlos syndrome; Idiopathic intercranial hypertension; Huntington's disease; IgA nephropathy; Multiple system atrophy; Rett syndrome; Sarcoidosis; Trachea oesophageal fistula; Tuberous sclerosis
Somanadhan 2023 ¹⁵¹	SR	6	Rare or undiagnosed condition; Cystic Fibrosis; Diabetes; Haemophilia; Juvenile idiopathic arthritis, Nephritic syndrome; Sickle cell anaemia
Genetic Alliance 2023 ⁵⁹	Primary study	6	Alstrom syndrome; Cavernoma; Chronic intestinal pseudo-obstruction; Deletion on chromosome 4q; Ehlers-Danlos syndrome; Sickle cell disease;
Lal 2022 ¹³⁷	SR	3 [†]	Juvenile idiopathic arthritis; Muscular dystrophies; Spina bifida
Hay 2022 ⁶⁹	Primary study	3	ANCA-associated Vasculitis; Bardet Biedl Syndrome; Tuberous sclerosis complex
Anestis 2020 ¹¹⁸	SR	2	Motor neuron disease, Multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's disease
Chudleigh 2016 ¹¹	Primary study	2	Cystic fibrosis; sickle cell disease
Costa 2022 ⁵⁰	Primary study	NR	n/a
Crowe 2019 ⁵¹	Primary study	NR	n/a
McMullan 2022 ⁸⁰	Primary study	NR	n/a
Peter 2022 ⁹⁵	Primary study	NR	n/a
Simpson 2021 ¹⁰¹	Primary study	NR	n/a
Specialised Healthcare Alliance 2023 ²⁴	Primary study	NR	n/a
Spencer-Tansley 2018 ¹⁰⁶	Primary study	NR	n/a
Spencer-Tansley 2022 ¹⁰⁷	Primary study	NR	n/a

Key: *=some non-rare diseases and rare cancers also included in this number; †=number includes a combination of different rare disease type subgroups as well as specific individual rare diseases; ‡Subset of diseases were reported but majority were not reported.

Appendix H: Numbers of primary studies and systematic reviews reporting inequities

Table A6. Numbers of primary studies and systematic reviews reporting inequities relating to subgroups in the rare disease community

	Diagnosis, n=primary studies (n=SRs)				Service access, n=primary studies (n=SRs)			
	Quant	Qual	MM*	Total	Quant	Qual	MM*	Total
Place of residence	0 (0)	2 (0)	0 (1)	2 (1)	6 (2)	6 (0)	5 (4)	17 (6)
Race/ethnicity	3 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	5 (0)	0 (1)	2 (1)	1 (4)	3 (6)
Gender	2 (0)	2 (0)	2 (1)	6 (1)	0 (0)	3 (0)	4 (5)	7 (5)
Socioeconomic status	0 (0)	4 (0)	1 (0)	5 (0)	1 (1)	1 (0)	3 (7)	5 (8)
Age (PLUS)	1 (0)	1 (0)	1 (1)	3 (1)	1 (0)	8 (3)	6 (9)	15 (12)
Disability (PLUS)	0 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	2 (0)	1 (0)	3 (0)
Total	6 (0)	13 (0)	4 (3)	23 (3)	8 (4)	22 (4)	20 (29)	50 (37)

*MM=Mixed methods; SRs which are not limited to one type of study are classified as mixed methods.

Table A7. Numbers of primary studies and systematic reviews reporting inequities shared across the rare disease community

	Diagnosis/ general population, n=primary studies (n=SRs)				Diagnosis/within RD population, n=primary studies (n=SRs)				Service access/ general population, n=primary studies (n=SRs)				Service access/ within RD population, n=primary studies (n=SRs)			
	Quant	Qual	MM*	Total	Quant	Qual	MM*	Total	Quant	Qual	MM*	Total	Quant	Qual	MM*	Total
Delayed diagnosis	3 (0)	18 (4)	5 (8)	26 (12)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lack of knowledge	1 (0)	11 (3)	6 (3)	18 (6)	0 (0)	1 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	4 (0)	18 (6)	10 (9)	32 (15)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)

Lack of information	2 (0)	8 (2)	7 (6)	17 (8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)	15 (3)	5 (9)	22 (12)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lack of services (general)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1)	10 (4)	4 (5)	15 (10)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lack of services (mental health)	0 (0)	1 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	4 (0)	10 (1)	10 (8)	24 (9)	1(0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)
Lack of services (dental)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lack of services (emergency)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	0 (1)	2 (1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lack of services (specialists)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)	3 (1)	4 (1)	9 (2)	3 (0)	0 (0)	1(0)	4 (0)
Lack of services (social care)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	6 (1)	5 (4)	12 (5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Lack of services (undiagnosed conditions)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)
Lack of care co-ordination	0 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)	3 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (0)	11 (3)	7 (7)	19 (10)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total	6 (0)	40 (9)	21 (17)	67 (26)	0 (0)	1 (0)	3 (0)	4 (0)	18 (1)	75 (19)	46 (44)	139 (64)	4 (0)	1 (0)	2 (0)	7 (0)

*MM=Mixed methods; SRs which are not limited to one type of study are classified as mixed methods.

